

V1. May 2018

D4.2. Ethics, Methodologies and standards

WP4 – Stratification: vulnerability multidimensional analysis

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

EFFICHRONIC has received funding from
the European Union's Health Programme
(2014-2020) under Grant Agreement 738127

Technical References

Deliverable No.	D4.2. – ETHICS, METHODOLOGIES AND STANDARDS
Dissemination Level¹	PU
Work Package	WP4 – STRATIFICATION: VULNERABILITY MULTIDIMENSIONAL ANALYSIS
Lead beneficiary	FICYT-CSPA-SESPA
Due date of deliverable	31/05/2018
Actual submission date	

Versions

Version	Person	Partner	Date
01	Marta Pisano Gonzalez An LD Boone	SESPA/CSPA FICYT	08 May 2018
02	Graham Baker	QISMET	15 May 2018
03	Bárbara Branchini	UVEG	17 May 2018
04	Marta Pisano Gonzalez An LD Boone	SESPA/CSPA FICYT	23 May 2018
##	Author 4	Partner short name	DD Month 20YY

Approved by Coordinator on: XX/XX/201X

Approved by Quality Manager on: XX/XX/201X

Statement of originality: This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. The publication reflects the author's views. The European Commission is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

¹PU = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

EFFICHRONIC is a project funded under the 3rd EU Health Programme and deals with one of its priorities, that is, to reduce the burden of major chronic diseases and increase the sustainability of health systems by providing evidence on the cost-efficiency of investments in evidenced-based prevention and management programme for chronic conditions by integrating social determinants of health.

The objective of this deliverable: “Ethics methodologies and standards”, of work package (WP) 4: “Stratification: vulnerability multidimensional analysis” is to describe the first steps taken in the EFFICHRONIC project to fulfil its specific Objective 2 (SO2): To design specific strategies to reach the targeted individual / groups identified / stratified to involve them in the program implementation.

The main purpose of this deliverable is to describe the design of specific strategies to reach targeted individuals and groups, that were previously identified and stratified, and to involve them in the implementation of the program. This leads to the description of how to involve specific (vulnerable) individuals in Public Health interventions, and specifically in chronic disease programs, and to formulate recommendations to recruit stratified individuals (including vulnerable populations) and involve them in these interventions.

The present deliverable is based on other deliverables, previously prepared by other members of the consortium: the general bases of communication and dissemination (Communication resources (D. 2.1)), the internal evaluation framework of EFFICHRONIC (Evaluation framework (D. 3.1)), as well as the definition of the clinical and socioeconomic variables necessary for the creation of the stratification instrument of the sample (List of clinical and social variables and MPI index (D4.1)).

The specific objectives of the deliverable are:

- Define the criteria and elaborate documents regarding the ethical considerations and data protection in the recruitment process, the training of the study population, and treatment of all data collected in EFFICHRONIC.
- Establish the criteria of clinical, socioeconomic and cultural vulnerability to define the inclusion and exclusion criteria of the sample for EFFICHRONIC.
- Determine vulnerability from a population point of view through generic indicators and geographical assessment in all the implementing countries.
- Establish a comprehensive framework of recruitment strategies and adherence to CDSMP workshops paying special attention to people from vulnerable population groups.
- Describe the standards used to develop this deliverable and draw conclusions from the previous objectives.

For the best understanding of the deliverable, the essential sections of ethics and recruitment of the vulnerable population have been described in the sections of methodology and results. The methodology section describes the specific processes of both undertaken and projected actions and an analysis of the different dimensions to achieve a maximum impact for recruitment at population and individual level.

The different products and documents elaborated for this deliverable of WP4 can be seen in the results section. Furthermore, it contains those products that, although not finalized, are the basis for the recruitment in practice and the organized and structured information that will be needed for the elaboration of guidelines as described in WP7.

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

As standards, we highlight those documents, protocols and guidelines agreed by the scientific community or recognized bodies that have been consulted and used to support this deliverable.

In the annexes we collect very specifically those documents that add value to the internal content of the deliverable and improve the understanding of the work carried out by the different partners of the EFFICHRONIC consortium.

D4.2 ETHICS, METHODOLOGIES AND STANDARDS

|| Table of contents

SECTION 1: PURPOSE, OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE	8
Section 1.1: The project EFFICHRONIC	8
Section 1.2: Purpose	9
Section 1.3: Objectives.....	10
Section 1.4: Scope	10
SECTION 2: METHODOLOGY	12
Section 2.1 Ethical Considerations and study design.....	12
2.1.1. Voluntary participation and informed consent.....	12
2.1.2. Data Protection	13
Section 2.2 The concept of vulnerability in EFFICHRONIC.....	13
2.2.1. The concept of vulnerability	13
2.2.2. The concept of vulnerability in EFFICHRONIC	14
Section 2.3 Recruitment methods based on population parameters	17
2.3.1. Background.....	17
2.3.2 Mapping in EFFICHRONIC.....	18
Section 2.4 Recruitment methods based on individual parameters.....	20
2.4.1. Scientific background on sampling, recruitment and engagement strategies design.....	20
2.4.2. Recruitment and engagement strategies approach: national workshops.....	25
SECTION 3: STANDARDS	27
Section 3.1 Ethical considerations.....	27
Section 3.2 Multidimensional Prognostic Index (MPI)	28
Section 3.3 Recruitment standards in vulnerable populations	28
SECTION 4: RESULTS	29
Section 4.1. Ethics.....	29
Section 4.2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria.....	29
Section 4.3. Recruitment methods based on population parameters	30
4.3.1. Asturias, Spain.....	30

4.3.2. Department of Hérault, France	33
4.3.3. The region of Genoa, Italy	35
4.3.4. United kingdom.....	36
Section 4.4 Template for workshops on recruitment strategies.....	36
Section 4.5 4 Recruitment methods based on individual parameters.....	37
4.5.1. Geopolitical recruitment	38
4.5.2. Recruitment through territorial organizations	38
4.5.3. Transversal recruitment by healthcare professionals.....	39
4.5.4 Transversal recruitment by professionals related to social work.....	39
4.5.5 Recruitment of persons in nursing homes and prisons	40
4.5.6 Recruitment by NGOs.....	40
4.5.7 Recruitment by civil society.....	41
SECTION 5: CONCLUSIONS.....	42
SECTION 6: ANNEXES.....	44

.....

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

GLOSSARY / LIST OF ACRONYMS

The following acronyms are used within this evaluation report:

A&E: Accident and Emergency

ADDP: Associação Protectora dos Diabéticos de Portugal, (Portuguese Diabetes Association)

CDSMP: Chronic Disease Self-Management Programme

CSPA: Consejería de Sanidad del Principado de Asturias (Regional Government of Health in Asturias)

CBPR Community-based Participatory Research

ENHW-FEANTSA: European Network of Homeless Health Workers- Fédération Européenne d'Associations Nationales Travaillant avec les Sans-Abri.

FDep: French Deprivation Index

FICYT: Fundación para el Fomento en Asturias de la Investigación Científica Aplicada y la Tecnología (Foundation for the support of the Applied Scientific Research and Technology in Asturias)

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

GP: General Practitioner

IMD: Index of Multiple Deprivation

IRIS: Institut de Relations Internationales et Strategiques (Institute of International Relations and Strategies)

INE: Instituto Nacional de Estadística (National Institute of Statistics)

INS: Istituto Nazionale di Statistica (National Institute of Statistics)

INSEE: Institut National de la Statistique et des Études Économiques (National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies)

LAU: Local Administrative Unit

MEDEA: Mortalidad en Áreas pequeñas Españolas y Desigualdades Socioeconómicas y ambientales (Mortality in small Spanish areas and socioeconomic and environmental inequalities)

MPI: Multidimensional Prognostic Index

NGO: Non-Governmental Organization

RDS: Respondent-driven sampling

SelfyMPI: Self-Administered Multidimensional Prognostic Index

SESPA: Servicio de Salud del Principado de Asturias (Public Health Service of Asturias)

WHO: World Health Organization

WP: Work Package

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

SECTION 1: PURPOSE, OBJECTIVES AND SCOPE

Section 1.1: The project EFFICHRONIC

Health systems are currently in full transformation. Demographic changes due to aging, the increasing prevalence of chronic disease and lifestyle conditions, together with the financial and budgetary crisis of recent years, require new models of health and social service provision to guarantee their sustainability. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), the global percentage of people living with chronic diseases can be estimated at around 35% of women and 29% of men and the average percentage is clearly influenced by the Social Determinants of Health².

Chronic diseases can be prevented by reducing risk factors related to high blood pressure, tobacco and/or alcohol consumption, hyperglycemia, stress or obesity amongst others. These risk factors are mostly linked to unhealthy sedentary lifestyles and could be successfully modified by using appropriate health practices. In line with this, a relevant number of programmes have shown evidence of the positive impact on prevention and management of chronic conditions, but there is scarcity of data on the efficiency and cost-benefit analysis of these programmes. The lack of scientific evidence might reduce the policy engagement and support to these programmes and prevents health systems from being more sustainable and efficient.

Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that socio-economic factors determine health disparities³. Recently, a lot of scientific evidence has been published that shows that socioeconomic and sociocultural differences can produce both short and long-term inequalities in relation to healthcare and self-care behaviour, both essential dimensions of chronic disease prevention and management^{4 5}. Furthermore, economic factors also condition the individuals' lifestyle with regard to their concerns about health and self-care as part of their way of life. Consequently, patients with chronic disorders who have a higher level of education, often have better skills to manage their condition and, therefore, show better health indicators than the ones with a lower educational or socioeconomic level^{6 7}. At the same time, the first are more likely to be interested in participating in community-based interventions, training programmes and research activities. Therefore, the impact of interventions aimed at increasing self-management skills and improving the health status of people with chronic diseases could be significantly greater in those individuals with low education and socio-economic vulnerability. **This project goes beyond the current state of the art on the management of chronic diseases, by carrying out a cost-efficiency analysis of an evidenced-based chronic disease prevention and management programme through the integration of social determinants of health.**

The project EFFICHRONIC aims to provide evidence on the positive return of investment and cost-efficiency of the application of the Chronic Disease Self-Management Programme (CDSMP) in 5 different European

² <http://www.who.int/es/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/noncommunicable-diseases>

³ Berkowitz, S. A., Traore, C. Y., Singer, D. E., & Atlas, S. J. (2015). Evaluating Area-Based socioeconomic status indicators for monitoring disparities within health care systems: Results from a primary care network. *Health Services Research, 50*(2), 398-417. doi:10.1111/1475-6773.12229

⁴ Vogler, S., Österle, A., & Mayer, S. (2015). Inequalities in medicine use in central eastern europe: An empirical investigation of socioeconomic determinants in eight countries. *International Journal for Equity in Health, 14*, 124.

⁵ Garcia-Gil, M., Elorza, J., Banque, M., Comas-Cufí, M., Blanch, J., Ramos, R., . . . Prieto-Alhambra, D. (2014). Linking of primary care records to census data to study the association between socioeconomic status and cancer incidence in southern europe: A nation-wide ecological study. *PloS One, 9*(10), e109706. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0109706

⁶ Cammett, M., Diwan, I., & Richards, A. (2018). A political economy of the middle east. Retrieved from <https://ebookcentral.proquest.com>

⁷ Muller, A. (2002). Education, income inequality, and mortality: a multiple regression analysis. *Bmj, 324*(7328), 23. Retrieved from <http://www.bmj.com/content/324/7328/23?linkType=FULL&ck=nck&resid=324/7328/23&journalCode=bmj>

countries (France, Italy, The Netherlands, Spain and UK) with a particular focus on specific factors health-related, medical, social, cultural and economic factors linked with a higher burden of chronic disorders in Europe.

Section 1.2: Purpose

The purpose of this deliverable is to describe the preparation of the sample, the target population of the project, from the ethical and methodological point of view, in order to draw conclusions and standards from it.

The present deliverable is based on the previous ones that have been prepared already by other members of the consortium: the general bases of communication and dissemination (Communication resources (D. 2.1)), the internal evaluation framework of EFFICHRONIC (Evaluation framework (D.3.1)), as well as the definition of the clinical and socioeconomic variables necessary for the creation of the stratification instrument of the sample (List of clinical and social variables and MPI index (D4.1)).

At this point in time, advances have been made in other general tasks of the project, and it is time to undertake the ones that derive from this deliverable "Ethics, Methodologies and Standards".

Once the stratification procedure was elaborated, several strategies have started to be designed to reach and involve people with vulnerability profiles based on the stratification algorithm. The conclusion was reached that there are mainly two main ways to recruit people for the programme:

- a) **Recruitment methods based on population parameters:** geographical mapping of areas with a higher percentage of vulnerable population was done. At a later stage, we can focus our strategies for individual recruitment in these areas by means of specifically designed actions.
- b) **Recruitment methods based on individual parameters:** the partners involved in the implementation will address specific individuals according to the previously defined selection criteria.

Prior to implementing the CDSMP programme, it is especially important and of great delicacy to carefully determine which definition of 'vulnerability' will be used, its scope, what kind of socio-economic determinants we are going to address and why, what will be the population that will benefit the most from our training action, what social, economic, cultural and also clinical criteria are going to be considered, where to localize the most disadvantaged people from a population point of view, how to access them, and finally, once captured, how to measure their vulnerability.

The elements described before are key factors in this phase of the project. We have to be prepared to leave our comfort zone of training people who usually attend the workshops to engage in proactive strategies to capture the vulnerable population, also called "hard to reach".

In EFFICHRONIC, this purpose is carried out considering the highest ethical and data protection levels as required by law and the scientific community at the present time.

The purpose of the information derived from this deliverable is not only internally, that is, to capture, stratify and measure the target population and elaborate Policy Recommendations. Its information may also be used by everyone who, in the future, needs to carry out actions related to health promotion and disease prevention in population groups that, apart from having a chronic disease and / or being a caregiver, also live in socio-culturally disadvantaged conditions.

Section 1.3: Objectives

The general objective of this deliverable, derived from the tasks of WP4, is to design specific strategies to reach the targeted individuals and groups to involve them in the programme implementation.

The specific objectives of the deliverable are:

- Define the criteria and elaborate documents with regard to ethics and data protection in the recruitment process, the training of the study population, and treatment of all data collected in EFFICHRONIC.
- Establish the criteria of clinical, socioeconomic and cultural vulnerability to define the inclusion and exclusion criteria of the sample for EFFICHRONIC.
- Determine the concept of 'vulnerability' from a population point of view through generic indicators and geographical assessment in all of the implementing countries.
- Establish a comprehensive framework of recruitment strategies and adherence to CDSMP workshops paying special attention to people from vulnerable population groups.
- Describe the standards used to develop this deliverable and draw conclusions from the previous objectives.

Section 1.4: Scope

In order to contextualize the document, the tasks of WP4 are briefly recalled:

- T4.1 Clinical variables identification.

This task has been developed previously. The target population of EFFICHRONIC is people with a chronic disease and / or their carers. Due to socio-demographic changes and current lifestyles, this group covers 35% of the general population. A key aspect to be able to draw conclusions from the intervention, is the determination of suitable criteria of greater or lesser clinical vulnerability in order to stratify the sample. **The clinical stratification criteria in EFFICHRONIC are adapted to a self-administered instrument: the Selfy-MPI.** The tool is based on the Multiple Prognostic Index (MPI), an internationally validated and standardized prognostic instrument which was originally developed to define the severity grade of mortality risk in geriatric patients with chronic conditions⁸. More detailed information can be found on this task and its development in D.4.1.

- T 4.2: Social determinants.

As previously commented in the summary, there are several socioeconomic and cultural variables that have been identified as potential factors for determining certain health disparities and, as a consequence, the aforementioned vulnerability. These factors have been related to poor management of chronic conditions (and / or health conditions in general). The vulnerability envisaged in EFFICHRONIC not only responds to the maximum use of the educational intervention programme, but has also opted for a broad and ambitious scope including a large target group. This way, the project aims at reaching a high level of inclusivity, considering economic (economic deprivation), cultural (low educational level), social (isolation, loneliness, and institutionalization), ethnical (ethnic minorities) and epidemiological (immigrants) criteria.

⁸ Pilotto A, Daragjati J, Veronese N. CGA and Clinical Decision-Making: The Multidimensional Prognostic Index. In: Pilotto A, Martin FC, eds. *Comprehensive Geriatric Assessment*. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2018:79-92

- T4.3: Algorithms for vulnerable individuals / groups identification

In EFFICHRONIC the described variables are included in an innovative way by means of the population stratification tool (Selfy-MPI). A person's vulnerability is caused by his/her clinical condition (of greater or lesser severity) and his/her social situation, and these aspects are not separable. They are held together within the individual, and jointly form the exact graduation of a more or less unfavorable condition. For this reason, the Selfy-MPI unites both concepts and establishes with a single questionnaire and one mathematical algorithm the global vulnerability of the individual. The scope of this new instrument, both for future studies and for a holistic approximation and understanding of the human being, is absolutely innovative. In Deliverable D.4.1, more detailed information can be found on this task and its development.

- T 4.4: Recruitment and engagement strategies design.

Once the stratification procedure has been defined, strategies have been designed to reach and involve people with vulnerability profiles based on the algorithm. The development of this deliverable specifically includes the ethics and methodology used for the development of this task. The information collected will be translated into the elaboration of documents on the strategy on how to capture of "hard to reach" participants as well as other documents related to ethical considerations and data protection within the project.

SECTION 2: METHODOLOGY

This section explains the methodology that was followed to achieve the objectives specified in section 1.3. Different methods were used according to the specific needs of each objective. A description of the ethical considerations, the approach to vulnerability in EFFICHRONIC and the theoretical background on recruitment on both population and individual level is defined. The fifth objective, description of standards, is developed in section 3. Section 4 mentions the specific results obtained for the execution of EFFICHRONIC following the below described methodology.

Section 2.1 Ethical Considerations and study design

Ethical considerations in recruitment for research are critical to promote the pursuit of truthful knowledge and prevent data falsification or fabrication. Ethical behaviour is also important for collaborative work as it encourages an environment of trust, accountability, and mutual respect among researchers. This is especially important when considering issues related to data sharing, co-authorship, copyright guidelines, confidentiality, and many other issues. Researchers must also adhere to ethical standards in order for the public to support and believe in the research. The public wants to be assured that researchers followed the appropriate guidelines for issues such as human rights, compliance with the law, conflicts of interest, safety, health standards and so on.

The particular study design of EFFICHRONIC is prospective, multicentric, open and set up as a before-after study. A control group was not considered in order to not exclude any of the individuals with specific vulnerability from the benefits of the intervention.

According to the local standards in all participating countries, a study protocol was submitted to the corresponding research ethical committees. This was the case for Asturias in Spain, Montpellier in France and Genoa in Italy. Each protocol was adapted to the specific realities of each study site.

In the UK and the Netherlands, it was not contemplated necessary to submit a study protocol to an ethics committee due to the fact that the CDSMP programme doesn't offer a specific treatment option and in the strict sense, EFFICHRONIC is not considered a clinical trial. It aims at changing people's health related habits and lifestyles, by means of different techniques in self-management, the three most important being formulating action plans, solving problems and decision making.

2.1.1. Voluntary participation and informed consent

Eligible participants will be informed in person of the objectives and the procedures of the CDSMP by the investigator or co-investigators and in writing by the participant information letter prior to being enrolled. This letter will include all information on how to participate, benefits and expected risks and terms of withdrawal from the study and is written in understandable language for the participants. Only after a sufficient period of reflection and after clarification of all questions, the participant is asked to sign two copies of the informed consent form and date by hand. A copy of the participant information letter and informed consent is handed over to the participant and the second copy of the consent form is kept by the centre.

Participation to the study is completely voluntary. The participants have the right to withdraw their consent from the study at any time for any reason and without jeopardizing their medical care. The investigator also has the right to withdraw participants in agreement with the sponsor or his delegate.

All the eligible participants will be provided with the CDSMP intervention. Furthermore, if a person does not comply with the inclusion criteria once the first contact is made, the CDSMP workshops will be offered to the person in question to not deprive anyone from the benefits of the intervention.

2.1.2. Data Protection

Data processing, communication and transfer will be carried out in accordance with the local data protection obligations of all participating study sites, as well as national and European requirements (EU Directive 96/46 on data protection). Participants are separately informed about data security in the participant's information letter.

As of May 25th 2018, this will be done in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016, on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data. The new regulation requires that users must be clearly informed about the extent of data collection, the legal basis for processing of personal data, how long data is retained, if data is being transferred to a third-party and/or outside the EU, and disclosure of any automated decision-making (not applicable in EFFICHRONIC). Users must be provided with contact details for data management and be informed of their rights under the GDPR⁹¹⁰.

At any time, participants can exercise their data protection rights. Only the research team and the health authorities (if applicable), who have the duty to maintain confidentiality, will have access to all collected study data. Only information that cannot be identified may be transmitted to third parties. In the event of information transmission to other countries, it will be carried out anonymously with a data protection level according to the Regulation (EU) 2016/679. The data will be collected and preserved until the study is finished in a codified way. The person responsible for data custody is responsible for the data file and treatment. At the end of the study, the data will be anonymized.

Section 2.2 The concept of vulnerability in EFFICHRONIC

2.2.1. The concept of vulnerability

Although there are multiple studies on social vulnerability, consensus and overall accepted indicators are still lacking. It remains difficult to understand and determine the factors that explain the reasons why some people, communities and groups have greater capacity than others to face situations of social disadvantage. In EFFICHRONIC the possible relationships between social vulnerability and disease are being studied.

According to Sánchez and Egea (2011), vulnerability is still a common and erroneous term to refer to poverty, marginalization and exclusion¹¹. These circumstances have favored the neglect of research and programs to address and reduce vulnerability, contributing to the maintenance of stereotypes and doubts to identify potentially vulnerable people, communities and disadvantaged groups.

Vulnerability is defined as: "The weakness or susceptibility of an individual or group that produces the perception of deterioration of factors related to protection and welfare. This causes a tendency in which all those variables that symbolize a state of normalization and social participation weaken towards one or several categories that define social exclusion. These categories are reflected in the well-being perceived by the individual, more concretely at personal, health-related, work, economic, cultural and social levels. In social

⁹ "Privacy notices under the EU General Data Protection Regulation". ico.org.uk. 2018-01-19.

¹⁰ "What information must be given to individuals whose data is collected?". European Commission .

¹¹ Sanchez D, Egea C. Enfoque de vulnerabilidad social para investigar las desventajas socioambientales: Su aplicación en el estudio de los adultos mayores. *Papeles de población*. 2011; 17(69): 151-185

work, several indicators and scales are used that determine the degree of vulnerability of the person, group or community¹².

Since the 1980s in Latin America, a "social vulnerability approach" has been developing that highlights the importance of dynamic socio-spatial structures and processes, determining the vulnerability of disadvantaged people and groups, emphasizing the understanding of the conditions of the daily life of people and communities to generate strategies focused on confronting and reducing vulnerability¹³. The focus of social vulnerability includes demographic and social vulnerability, since in both cases demographic variables would allow identifying vulnerable groups and socio-demographic risks. The Economic Survey of Latin America and the Caribbean (2001) defines it this way: "Demographic vulnerability refers to the risks, weaknesses or disadvantages that communities, households and people face as a result of the intervention of factors (trends, characteristics, behaviors) of demographic origin"¹⁴.

Unlike the concepts of poverty or social exclusion, social vulnerability expresses potential in terms of ability to cope with and / or avoid unwanted threats¹⁵.

In 1922, Mary Richmond published the book titled "What is social case work?". The described method was based on individual attention with the aim of developing personal strengths and potentials as a means to achieve self-sufficiency and a more active participation in the efforts to achieve the goals set by the person, admitting their reliance on family and the influence of their social environment.

Other pioneers of social work such as Gordon Hamilton, Charlotte Towle or Helen Harris, among others, offered intervention models based on the individual attention to people, with the aim of developing their personality, and as a means to achieve self-sufficiency and participation in the achievement of objectives. This method continues to be a reference for social health workers, as a means of empowering people and involving the family and community environment.

The "assets" of the chronic patient would be the set of strategies, tools and response mechanisms, both from the individual and social or institutional (social networks and services) point of view. The study and analysis of these assets and their deficits is essential to modify personal, group or community behaviours and attitudes that prevent and/or hinder healing well, or the stabilization of the disease process.

2.2.2. The concept of vulnerability in EFFICHRONIC

EFFICHRONIC will implement the CDSMP in those groups of society that are regularly exposed to the negative effect of the conditions in which they are born, grow up, live, work and get older, i.e., the social determinants of health, responsible for the unfair and avoidable differences in health. These groups will be referred to as "vulnerable" during the project EFFICHRONIC.

1. Vulnerable groups

As already expressed in the previous descriptions of vulnerability the concept is more intuitive than analytical, and the social sciences use this term with a broad meaning.

¹² Fernández-García, De Lorenzo, Vázquez. *Diccionario de Trabajo Social* (eds), 2012).

¹³ Busso G. (2005). *Pobreza, exclusión y vulnerabilidad social. Usos, limitaciones y potencialidades para el diseño de políticas de desarrollo y de población. Ponencia presentada en las VIII Jornadas Argentinas de Estudios de Población, Tandil, Argentina. 2005; 12-14.*

¹⁴ Kaztman R. *Notas sobre la medición de la vulnerabilidad social. 2000 (CEPAL)*

¹⁵ Elisabeth Schröder-Butterfill E, Mariani R, *A framework for understanding old-age vulnerabilities, Ageing Soc. 2006 January ; 26(1): 9–35.*

In EFFICHRONIC the definition used by international organizations, such as the World Health Organization¹⁶ and the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies¹⁷, will be used, being, “the diminished capacity of an individual or group to anticipate, cope with, resist and recover from the impact of a natural or manmade hazard”.

Commonly, the term vulnerability refers to marginalised people or people living in poverty. Vulnerable people would equate to “poor”, “marginalised”, “deprived” or “disadvantaged” and would typically include: homeless people; sex workers; drug users; people living with HIV; people from sexual minority communities; asylum seekers, refugees (also called displaced migrants); people from ethnic minority communities (cultural and linguistic minorities); traveller families (including Roma people); prisoners; etc.^{18,19} However, vulnerability can equally appear even if the individual has his/her basic needs (food, housing, etc.) covered, but instead, lacks family ties or social relationships. “Vulnerability is most often associated with poverty, but it can also arise when people are isolated, insecure and defenseless in the face of risk, shock or stress”²⁰.

In a report by the Spanish Red Cross from 2006, vulnerability is defined as an “intermediate zone” in which everybody can enter at certain moments in life and due to quite different reasons, for example, a catastrophic or life changing event can render everybody vulnerable. “The zone of social vulnerability is located between the zone of social integration (a stable job, solid social and family pillars) and the zone of social exclusion (jobless, social isolation, lack of family ties), thus becoming a more unstable zone, with precarious jobs, intermittent periods of employment and unemployment and with weak social and family relationships”²¹. The report captures key profiles of individuals in a vulnerable situation, in the first place, young homeless foreigners and native homeless, followed by young and qualified foreign women without income or with family problems and native elderly women.

In line with the above, two broad dimensions of the vulnerability concept are described in EFFICHRONIC: a social and an individual dimension.

- a) The social dimension of the concept perceives vulnerability taking into consideration societal factors and the people’s environment deriving from social and economic structures. Therefore, vulnerable people are considered the socioeconomically disadvantaged, excluded from participating fully in society or suffering from stigma and discrimination, violence and abuse or restrictions in exercising civil and political rights.
- b) The individual dimension considers the physical and psychological aspects of the individual that lead to a situation of vulnerability. The chronically ill, disabled, fragile elderly or people suffering mental health problems can be under severe stress and, consequently, be in a situation of vulnerability.

The EFFICHRONIC project will use the term “vulnerable” as an umbrella concept which includes people suffering from social exclusion and socio-economic hardship, as well as people under physical or psychological stress. The following graph aims to capture the analytical approach to vulnerability that will be adopted by the EFFICHRONIC project.

¹⁶ http://www.who.int/environmental_health_emergencies/vulnerable_groups/en/

¹⁷ See <http://www.ifrc.org/en/what-we-do/disaster-management/about-disasters/what-is-a-disaster/what-is-vulnerability/>

¹⁸ Department of Health (2002) *Addressing inequalities. Reaching the hard to reach groups. A practical aid to implementation in primary care.* London: Department of Health.

¹⁹ Flanagan SM & Hancock B (2010) *Reaching the hard to reach' - lessons learned from the VCS (voluntary and community Sector). A qualitative study*

²⁰ See <http://www.ifrc.org/en/what-we-do/disaster-management/about-disasters/what-is-a-disaster/what-is-vulnerability/>

²¹ Cruz Roja (2006) *Informe Anual Sobre la Vulnerabilidad Social 2006. Estudio de la Vulnerabilidad Social.*

Figure 1 : Concept of Vulnerability

2. Hard-to-reach

A related concept for the EFFICHRONIC project is the fact that vulnerable groups are usually hard-to-reach and tend to experience the least satisfactory access to health services. Flanagan and Hancock (2010) suggest several reasons why these groups may not be accessible for the health services: (i) because they lack the choice to attend; (ii) because of stigma; (iii) because health services themselves create barriers that impede people from attending; (iv) because they have fallen through the care net (people let down by the system); (v) because of cultural differences between subaltern groups and public authorities or representatives among other reasons. Eventually, reaching vulnerable people may be also difficult because they may not associate with other members of society. Populations with a high proportion of non-associative members are defined by individual attributes such as physiological factors or health status. There is not often an overriding reason for people not socializing and a substantial proportion of population not having strong social links with other members and, indeed, many might even resist such contact²². Reaching “non-associative” individuals (such as, people with mental health problems or elderly people living alone) may entail different recruitment strategies than identifiable groups of vulnerable people (i.e. Roma people, travellers, asylum seekers).

The EFFICHRONIC project focuses on those vulnerable people who are non-users of health care services (“they don’t come to see us”; “they would not seek support from the usual avenues”) (Flanagan and Hancock, 2010). Hence, they are “hard-to reach” for the health services and have traditionally been “underserved”.

3. Contemplation of vulnerability in EFFICHRONIC

The CDSMP methodology requires a certain intellectual capacity, physical mobility, the ability to make personal choices and a certain stability in one’s life project necessary to be able to fully participate and benefit

²² Thompson S. and Phillips D. (2007) *Reaching and Engaging Hard-to-Reach Populations With a High Proportion of Nonassociative Members*, *Qualitative Health Research*, Volume 17 Number 9, pp. 1292-1303.

from the programme. For example, people sleeping on the street every night (homeless people) might find it very hard to engage with the basics of the CDSMP, such as attending a weekly two-and-a-half hour workshop for six consecutive weeks or making use of the educational material provided with the training course. However, people sleeping in temporary accommodation or shelters or living in supported shared flats with other housemates might be candidates to join the CDSMP. Likewise, people with severe mental health problems might be unable to even sit in a 10-16 people meeting and actively take part in the workshop; but people with minor mental health conditions might be totally suitable to join this type of programmes.

Another key element concerning the CDSMP training is the leaders' participation. These are usually (although not exclusively) non-professionals (peers) with one or more chronic conditions who voluntarily facilitate the workshop using a detailed, scripted manual (Stanford 2016). Hence, identifying, recruiting and managing suitable leaders from certain vulnerable groups should be a matter of concern and requires careful thinking.

Section 2.3 Recruitment methods based on population parameters

As mentioned before, the social dimension of vulnerability considers societal factors and the people's environment deriving from social and economic structures. Areas classified as vulnerable in each of the participating regions are likely to harbour a large amount of target population for EFFICHRONIC and recruiting efforts should be focussing on these areas. Nevertheless, within a geographical area of high deprivation there will be pockets of low-deprivation, and vice versa, so this strategy should not be exclusive.

2.3.1. Background

A first approach to detect vulnerable population is made from the concept of deprivation, a term that emerged in the 1980s in Great Britain, in the context of the analysis of social inequalities in health. The term refers to the lack of access to resources, whether material (housing, food ...) or social (community integration, formal participation in social life and institutions ...). Townsend defined it as a state of observable and demonstrable disadvantage in relation to the community, society or nation to which an individual, a family or a group belongs²³.

Since this term has been used in the 1980s, multiple approaches to deprivation have been made based on simple or compound socioeconomic indicators combined in an index. Among the first deprivation indices described in literature, it is worth mentioning the Townsend and Carstairs indices, pioneers in this type of studies²⁴. Both indices include four variables: unemployment, non-car ownership and household overcrowding common to both indices; and non-home ownership in the Townsend index, and low social class, in the Carstairs index. Both indices are additive one-dimensional compounds and present a series of methodological problems, such as the lack of weighting of the variables that make up the index and the imposition of a threshold of deprivation (Rodero²⁵), which makes them inappropriate. Jarman proposed one of the first indexes of deprivation aimed at measuring health inequalities²⁶. This index uses a statistical technique similar to the previous ones but adds a weighting of the variables, thus solving one of the problems of statistical additive techniques. In addition to the previous variables, it includes four others: proportion of single-parent families, children younger than 5 years of age, old people living alone and recently arrived immigrants. Subsequently, multivariate techniques for the preparation of indexes of deprivation were beginning to be used, becoming one of the preferred ones the principal component analysis.

²³ Townsend P; Phillimore P and Beattie A. *Health and Deprivation: Inequality and the North*. Routledge, London. 1988

²⁴ Castairs V and Morris R. *Deprivation, mortality and resource allocation*. *Community Medicine* (1989), 11(4): 64-372

²⁵ Rodero Cosano, ML. "Tesis." *Reformulación del índice de privación. El caso de la Comunidad Autónoma de Andalucía*. 2015.

²⁶ Jarman, B. "Identification of underprivileged areas." *British Medical Journal* 286 (1983): 1705-1709.

The Quebec index of material and social deprivation combines six indicators in two components: a first component of material deprivation, reflecting variations in education, employment and income; and a second component associated with the social aspects of deprivation: marital status (separated, divorced or widowed), single-parent families and people living alone²⁷.

Measuring the deprivation of a geographical area implies losing part of the richness of the concept, since the percentage of individuals experiencing a certain type of simple deprivation, or a combination of various kinds of deprivation can be measured, but the different types of deprivation of an individual cannot be measured.

At this level, deprivation rates measure the proportion of families in a given geographic unit with a combination of circumstances that indicate a low standard of living, a high need for services, or both²⁸.

However, it should not be forgotten that the generic deprivation indexes have shown not to measure deprivation well enough in rural areas²⁹ and to have different components depending on the geographical context: unemployment is the variable with most weight in the urban environment, while in rural areas other variables such as the lack of basic services in the home and the unavailability of cars have more significance. Shaw, in 1979, had already pointed out some of the distinctive features of rural deprivation such as deprivation of opportunities in health, education and recreational services; and the deprivation of mobility: lack of transportation and inaccessibility of jobs and services. This leads to the need to deal separately with urban deprivation of the rural one. That is, to use a method of measuring deprivation that is sensitive to the type of geographical area.

Finally, in relation to the geographic unit to be used, it should be noted that, although the municipality is an appropriate unit for detecting socioeconomic problems and it is the spatial unit that has better information, it presents problems when it is used in macro-urban areas. The most important problem is the excessive aggregation that implies incorporating them in their corresponding municipality, preventing the detection of marginal areas in the cities.

2.3.2 Mapping in EFFICHRONIC

For EFFICHRONIC, existing national and local indexes were contemplated in all participating countries to determine vulnerable areas with a high percentage of target population.

The data source used to extract the necessary information for the elaboration of the indexes is the Population Census, available online in the official statistical pages of three of the countries of the consortium (INE in Spain, INSEE in France and ISTAT in Italy). Despite its limitations, Population Censuses have been considered the source of demographic information par excellence, since they meet two essential conditions for a multitude of research works: 100% coverage of individuals and availability of very diverse demographic variables.

As a geographical unit, the territorial unit corresponding to the municipality is used (Local Administrative Unit (LAU) 2 of Eurostat). However, when possible (large cities and in case of information available) an infra-municipal territorial disaggregation is made, corresponding to the census in Spain and Italy, and IRIS (Institut de relations internationales et stratégiques) in France.

²⁷ Pampalon R, Raymond G. "A Deprivation Index for Health and Welfare Planning in Quebec." *Chronic Diseases in Canada* 21, no. 3 (2000): 104-113.

²⁸ Bartley M, Blane D, 1994, *Appropriateness Of Deprivation Indexes Must Be Ensured*, *British Medical Journal*, Vol: 309, Pages: 1479-1479, Issn: 0959-8138

²⁹ Barnett S, Roderick P, Martin D, Diamond I. "A multilevel analysis of the effects of rurality and social deprivation on premature limiting long term illness." *Journal Epidemiology Community Health* 55 (2001): 44-51.

2.3.2.1 Asturias, Spain

In Spain, the data from the 2001 Census have been used. The last census conducted in Spain in 2011 was only carried out in a sample of 10% of the population for economic reasons with the consequent loss of exhaustiveness of the information. However, within an ongoing research project of the Spanish Society of Epidemiology, the conclusion was reached that similar results were obtained when creating vulnerability maps with data from 2001 compared to 2011.

The first deprivation studies in Spain were related to studies on health inequalities and were derived from existing foreign indices. Worth mentioning is the index of the research group of the MEDEA project carried out by Domínguez Berjón and partners in 2008 based on the principal component analysis³⁰. This index was designed for the analysis of disadvantaged geographic areas within large cities. It combines five indicators: manual workers, unemployment, temporary employees, insufficient education in young people and, insufficient education in the total population. For EFFICHRONIC, the MEDEA index was used for large cities and for rural areas, a specific index (without external validation was elaborated based on principal components analysis. indicators indicated in the methodological section were included. This analysis showed a first dimension that contained a series of indicators related to geographical and social isolation: aging, one-person households, families without a vehicle and people that are separated, divorced or widowed. This component explained 40% of the total variance of the 15 initial indicators. Considering that this component explained an important part of the target vulnerable population, it was decided to develop a rural vulnerability index combining the four indicators that saturated in the first dimension by extracting a single axis by applying main components.

2.3.2.2 Hérault, France

The most widely validated index of social deprivation for France is called FDep (French Deprivation Index) and this was used to design the vulnerability maps of the participating French region in EFFICHRONIC. This indicator allows the adaptation to the rural and urban context from the stratification of the same on the different typologies of the municipalities³¹. In addition, it has been used at the disaggregated level (according to IRIS), the smallest geographical unit in France (average of 2,000 h) for which the demographic and socioeconomic data of the census are available. It includes 4 indicators: percentage of unemployed, percentage of workers in the active population, percentage of high school graduates and disposable income per consumption unit.

2.3.2.3 Genoa, Italy

In Italy, Caranci developed an index that inserts 5 socioeconomic indicators: percentage of unemployed among the active population, percentage of rented housing, percentage of population whose educational level is equal to or lower than the primary school diploma, percentage of single-parent families and housing density (occupants / 100 m²)³². The Caranci index is used for the metropolitan area of Genoa and the Crevari index³³ is used for the city of Genoa (territorial disaggregation). The latter includes the same indicators as the Caranci index with the exception of the percentage of single-parent families, data that are not available on a census level.

³⁰ Domínguez-Berjón MF, Borrell C, Cano-Serral G, Esnaola S, Nolasco A, Pasarín MI et al. "Construcción de un índice de privación a partir de datos censales en grandes ciudades españolas." *Gaceta Sanitaria* 22, no. 3 (2008): 179-187.

³¹ Challier B, Viel JF. "Pertinence et validité d'un nouvel indice composite français mesurant la pauvreté au niveau géographique." *Rev. Epidém. et Santé Publ.* 49 (2001): 41-50.

³² Caranci N, Biggeri A, Grisotto L, Pacelli B, Spadea T, Costa G. "L'indice di deprivazione italiano a livello di sezione di censimento: definizione, descrizione e associazione con la mortalità." *Epidemiol Prev* 34, no. 4 (2010): 167-176.

³³ Test A, Ivaldi E and Busi A. Genoa Index of Deprivation: An index of deprivation for geographical areas. www.researchgate.net 2011 (accessed August 2017)

2.3.2.4 United Kingdom

A national system called the Index of Multiple Deprivation (IMD) exists in the UK and combines information from seven domains to produce an overall relative measure of deprivation³⁴. The domains are combined using the following weights: Income Deprivation, Employment Deprivation, Education, Skills and Training Deprivation, Health Deprivation and Disability, Crime, Barriers to Housing and Services and Living Environment Deprivation. The weights were derived from academic literature on poverty and deprivation, as well as the levels of robustness of the indicators. The IMD is very widely used and is the national way of measuring deprivation in both rural and urban areas.

2.3.2.5 Rotterdam, the Netherlands

Population census in The Netherlands differs from other European countries since 1978. Individual census questionnaires are no longer used and the country conducts a register-based census. Unfortunately, this census method does not allow constructing deprivation indices as in other European countries and no vulnerability maps were designed for this country. Recruitment at this study site will have to be performed based on individual recruitment strategies only.

Section 2.4 Recruitment methods based on individual parameters

Developing effective strategies to reach out to vulnerable individuals and groups (objective 3) is certainly key to the success of the project. Those identified individuals will be recruited to receive chronic disease self-management training through the participation in the CDSMP. With the purpose of recruiting people individually, EFFICHRONIC will identify and learn from successful and innovative experiences of sampling, recruiting vulnerable populations in health-related interventions around Europe and worldwide, and will adapt the insights and methodologies to the specific goals and different contexts of the project.

As part of the overall communication strategy of EFFICHRONIC, different workshops and events have been planned. These aim at engaging with public health and chronic care experts, professionals and decision-makers. The first workshop seeks to present EFFICHRONIC goals, frameworks and methodologies to a wide community of people in each national setting, to consider different strategies for reaching out vulnerable populations, and to discuss and co-produce an evaluation framework to assess the efficiency and cost-benefit of the chronic care interventions that promote patient empowerment, with a special focus on the social determinants of health.

2.4.1. Scientific background on sampling, recruitment and engagement strategies design

The current background section has been produced with the goal of encouraging and supporting professionals, experts and decision-makers' discussions to develop effective strategies to reach out the identified vulnerable individuals and groups (objective 3).

It has also served as the basis for the organization of National Workshops to facilitate discussions in all of the countries of the participating members of the EFFICHRONIC consortium during the initial phase of the project. In this section the main evidence which identifies and suggests a number of experiences for sampling, recruiting and retaining vulnerable people in health interventions, is shown.

³⁴ <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/english-indices-of-deprivation-2015>

Reviewing literature on research on hidden and hard-to-reach socially disadvantaged groups, it is suggested to use non-probability sampling techniques, including snowballing through social networks; venue-based time-location; respondent-driven sampling; targeted sampling; capture-recapture; adaptive sampling; sampling through community organizations; etc³⁵. Below, only a number of these techniques will be discussed.

Before proceeding to the analysis of specific sampling and recruiting techniques, it is worth mentioning that the literature recognizes the importance of tailoring recruitment methods to the culture of the target population if it is from a specific ethnic minority³⁶. These methods include: the use of posters and flyers illustrated with ethnic minority individuals (.e.g. African Americans) posted in doctors' offices, clinics, churches, hairdressers, and barbershops; hiring people from the community to recruit by making presentations at churches, community centres, health fairs, or events; making telephone calls to potential participants; etc.

2.4.1.1 Strategies for Sampling and Recruiting in the CDSMP

CDSMP has been applied to low income, urban or rural people and people from minority populations (Hispanic) of North America and elsewhere. The strategies for sampling and recruiting vulnerable populations tend to be limited to advertising the CDSMP courses on the local media, on community organizations bulletins and at health centres. The CDSMP Administration/Implementation Manual (Stanford 2016) mentions the local media (radio, TV), church bulletins, school newsletters, social clubs, etc. It also suggests the use of electronic media. However, the common hard-to-reach characteristic of the individuals and groups that are the target of the EFFICHRONIC project poses challenges that are not directly addressed by the Stanford Administration/Implementation Manual³⁷.

2.4.1.2 Strategies for Sampling and Recruiting at health organizations

As mentioned above, elderly people or people with mental health problems seek regular care from their primary care or mental health centre and, if their health situation worsens, they may be taken to hospital. Thus, all these health care sites can be places to identify and recruit them. EFFICHRONIC may consider recruiting individuals through General Practitioner (GP) practices, at the hospital wards or at the A&E door.

Examples from literature

Recruiting at an Urban Community Health Center in Alaska³⁸.

In order to be qualified as a workshop participant in this study, the individual had to attend 1 or more sessions of a CDSMP or diabetes training workshop between April and October 2009. Self-management training was widely advertised at the clinics and patients with diabetes were actively recruited. The control group was selected from the Community Health Center registry of patients with diabetes who did not attend any self-management training beyond usual care.

Targeting frequent users of Primary Health Care services³⁹.

³⁵ Bonevski, B., Randell, M., Paul, C., Chapman, K., Twyman, L., Bryant, J., . . . Hughes, C. (2014). *Reaching the hard-to-reach: A systematic review of strategies for improving health and medical research with socially disadvantaged groups*. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 14(1), 42-42. doi:10.1186/1471-2288-14-42

³⁶ (Burns et al. 2008).

³⁷ Stanford University (2016) *Stanford Self-Management Programs. Administration/Implementation Manual*.

³⁸ Alaska Section of Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion (2013). *Clinical Outcomes of Urban Community Health Center Patients Who Participated in Self-Management Classes*. *Chronicle Volume 5, Issue 2, July*.

This study aimed to examine factors associated with acceptance and completion rates of the CDSMP among frequent users of health care services. It was conducted in 4 family medicine groups, including 38 practices, in the Saguenay-Lac-Saint-Jean region of the Province of Quebec (Canada). Patients had to be aged between 18 and 80 years, with at least one chronic disease (diabetes, cardiovascular, respiratory or musculoskeletal disease or chronic pain) and targeted by their family physician as a frequent user of health care services who would benefit from participating in a case management intervention by a primary care nurse. The family physicians received a list of their frequent users (who consulted the Emergency Department and/or were hospitalized three or more times in the previous year). The CDSMP was explained and offered to each patient by his or her case management nurse. Groups included patients with different chronic diseases. In total, 167 frequent users of services were recruited for case management and were also invited to participate in the CDSMP. 60 patients out of the 167 accepted the participation in the programme.

Homeless people attending hospital A&E⁴⁰

Homeless people have complex problems. GP enhanced care (Pathway) has shown benefits. A randomised, -parallel arm trial was performed at two large inner city hospitals in London. Inpatient homeless adults were randomly allocated to either standard care (all management by the hospital-based clinical team) or enhanced care with input from a homeless care team. The hospital data system provided healthcare usage information, and questionnaires were used to assess quality of life. 206 patients were allocated to enhanced care and 204 to usual care. Length of stay (up to 90 days after admission) did not differ between groups (standard care 14.0 days, enhanced care 13.3 days). Average re-attendance at the emergency department within a year was 5.8 visits in the standard care group and 4.8 visits with enhanced care, but this decrease was not significant. - Quality of life scores after discharge (in 108 patients) improved with enhanced care (EQ-5D-5L score increased by 0.12 [95% CI 0.032 to 0.22] compared with 0.03 [-0.1 to 0.15; p=0.076] with standard care). The proportion of people sleeping on the streets after discharge was 14.6% in the standard care arm and 3.8% in the enhanced care arm (p=0.034). The quality-of-life cost per quality-adjusted life-year was £26,000. The Pathway approach doesn't alter length of stay but improves quality of life and reduces street -homelessness.

2.4.1.3 Strategies for Sampling and Recruiting at the neighbourhood level

Where do the elderly living alone necessarily go to meet their basic needs?

“Seville with you” (Todos Contigo). New Health Foundation (Seville, Spain)⁴¹.

The community workers of the project “Sevilla Contigo” of the New Health Foundation approach their target population at three key places at the neighbourhood: the local shop (in particular, the Bakery – “where old people with few resources buy bread, because it is the cheapest”), the Parish (or the local faith group) and the Pharmacy (elderly people with various chronic conditions need to buy medicines). Thus, the project approaches these three venues and works closely with shop-keepers, priests, parish groups, as well as retail pharmacists to identify vulnerable people and include them in the project. The “Sevilla Contigo” project is also considering working closely with the neighbourhood postman to identify target individuals.

³⁹ Hudon C et al. (2016) *The Chronic Disease Self-Management Program: the experience of frequent users of health care services and peer leaders*, *Family Practice*, Vol. 33, No. 2, 167–171.

⁴⁰ Hewett N et al. (2016) *Clin Med (Lond)* Randomised controlled trial of GP-led in-hospital management of homeless people ('Pathway'), 16 (3): 223-9.

⁴¹ <http://todoscontigo.newhealthfoundation.org/sevilla-contigo-ciudad-compassiva-2/>

2.4.1.4. Sampling and recruiting through community organizations

Voluntary and Community Sector organizations (Non-governmental Organizations (NGOs), charity and religious groups, etc.) who work with vulnerable populations can be a useful partner in identifying individuals, families and groups. Community organizations' registries of the people they are providing support to – such as the Caritas registry described below- can be a useful sampling tool. Community organizations' volunteers could be really helpful in recruiting and incorporating potential participants into EFFICHRONIC.

Using the Cáritas registry to identify homeless individuals or families⁴²

Description of the living and housing conditions and health status among people attended by Caritas Barcelona and living in substandard housing. In Brussels: European Network of Homeless Health Workers⁴³ (ENHW-FEANTSA).

The report describes the socio-demographic characteristics, housing conditions and health status of these families before undergoing rehousing. The study population was obtained from the Caritas registry: several families (or single persons) living in substandard dwelling conditions (inadequate housing habitability conditions or overcrowding) as assessed by Caritas' social workers from the Direct Attention Service, were identified and invited to participate in the study. Those who agreed to participate were interviewed face-to-face by a trained interviewer at the Caritas' centre in Barcelona between September and December 2012 (n=175). Also, 145 additional Caritas users with difficulties paying housing costs (rent or mortgage) and having been attended by Caritas's Housing Mediation Service were also interviewed. This study is part of the SOPHIE research⁴⁴, a project funded by the European Community's Seventh Framework Programme. It aims to generate new evidence on the impact of structural policies on health inequalities, and to develop innovative methodologies for the evaluation of these policies in Europe.

Diabetes prevention and diagnosis: reaching out to vulnerable groups in Portugal

The Portuguese Diabetes Association – APDP - has been partnering with the Ernest Roma Foundation since 2009 to carry out a series of projects aiming to promote diabetes prevention, early diagnosis and proper diabetes management for the poorest and most marginalised. Initiatives include large screening and diagnosis campaigns, as well as educational workshops in more disadvantaged neighbourhoods and training courses for social workers and other personal care assistants. The joint initiative has been far-reaching, with currently more than 11,000 people screened. Coordinated under the auspices of the Portuguese Programme for Diabetes, the project is one of the major initiatives to promote healthier lifestyles amongst the poorest and most marginalised populations who are struggling with access to healthcare, information and training and therefore have a higher risk of developing diabetes⁴⁵.

Alternative registries or sources of information on people in need might be held by other social organizations, such as the Red Cross or Fédération Européenne d'Associations Nationales Travaillant avec les Sans-Abri AISBL (FEANTSA). In Asturias, the Albergue Covadonga y la Asociación Albéniz, through Faciam⁴⁶ are FEANTSA members.

⁴² Ana M. Novoa, Davide Malmusi, Julia Ward, Fernando Díaz, Jordi Bosch, Mercè Darnell, Carme Trilla, Carme Borrell (2014)

⁴³ <http://www.feantsa.org/en/newsletter/2015/01/14/european-network-of-homeless-health-workers-issue-20?bcParent=27>

⁴⁴ <http://www.sophie-project.eu/index.htm>

⁴⁵ www.apdp.pt or www.fundacaoernestoroma.org

⁴⁶ <http://faciam.org/faciam/>

2.4.1.5 Venue based time-location

Venue based time-location has been widely used for conducting research and developing interventions with hard-to-reach groups such as men who have sex with men, homeless people or drug users. The key principle is that these populations are approached in those places and at those times when they tend to meet up and gather. For example, homeless people may be approached at a charity association at the time meals are served.

The Homeless People Survey is a Spain-wide survey conducted with homeless individuals who attend social accommodation and/or feeding services in towns with a population bigger than 20.000. The survey was conducted between February 13th and March 25th; as that is the period when the demand for sleeping and meals is higher. *In Asturias, 6 centres (3 providing accommodation; 3 providing meals) participated in the EPSH-2012.⁴⁷

The methodology is quite sophisticated though and includes three basic components: formative research to learn the venues, times, and methods to recruit the people; monthly sampling frames of eligible venues and day-time periods that met attendance, logistical, and safety criteria; and recruitment of participants in accordance with randomly generated venue calendars⁴⁸.

2.4.1.6 Respondent-driven sampling

Respondent-driven sampling (RDS) is a technique in which participants recruit one another, similar to snowball sampling. It is particularly used with “hidden” populations such as injection drug users, men who have sex with men and commercial sex workers. Typically, other standard sampling methods (including targeted sampling and time-location sampling) reveal less useful to engage with these populations. The process starts by “selecting a small number of initial participants (“seeds”) from the target population who are asked—and typically provided financial incentive—to recruit their contacts in the population. The sampling proceeds with current sample members recruiting the next wave of sample members, continuing until the desired sample size is reached. Participants are usually allowed to recruit up to three other contacts in order to ensure sampling continues even if some sample members do not recruit”⁴⁹.

2.4.1.7 Combinations of recruitment strategies

Combination of recruitment strategies⁵⁰

Background—Community-based Participatory Research (CBPR) may be an important strategy for partnering with and reaching populations who bear a greater burden of illness but have been historically difficult to engage. A Community Action Board of 20 East Harlem (Manhattan, USA) residents, leaders and advocates used CBPR to compare the effectiveness of different strategies in recruiting and enrolling adults with pre-diabetes into a peer-led diabetes prevention intervention.

Methods—The Board created 5 different recruitment strategies:

⁴⁷ <http://www.ine.es/prensa/np761.pdf>

⁴⁸ MacKellar DA et al. (2007) “Surveillance of HIV Risk and Prevention Behaviors of Men Who Have Sex with Men—A National Application of Venue-Based, Time-Space Sampling”, *Public Health Rep.* 2007; 122(Suppl 1): 39–47.

⁴⁹ Goel S and Salganik MJ (2010) Assessing respondent-driven sampling, *PNAS* 107 (15): 6743-6747. <http://www.pnas.org/content/107/15/6743.full.pdf>

⁵⁰ Horowitz CR et al. (2009) Effective Recruitment of Minority Populations through Community-Led Strategies, *Am J Prev Med.* 37 (6 Suppl 1): 195–200

- Through clinicians: educating local clinicians about pre-diabetes, giving them a toolkit and referral cards so clinicians could easily refer patients. Followed up with all clinicians through phone calls, visits and educational sessions.
- At large public events like health fairs, street fairs and farmer's markets. Partners set up tables with banners, giveaways and community members, who were greeters, encouraged their neighbours to learn.
- By organizing special local recruitment events, such as Stop Diabetes Day (advertised in local newspapers, flyers, e-mail blasts and at local businesses and housing developments. These included live music, dancing, healthy foods and giveaways specifically tailored to identifying potential enrollees).
- At local organizations and garnering their support in approaching their clients about the study.
- Partner-led approach in which community partners developed and managed the recruitment efforts at their sites. Community advocates spearheaded these efforts and voiced their needs to make recruitment work at their organizations. They explained and championed the study to their own constituents and invited researchers into the process once people understood the study and showed interest in taking part. In this process, they also told the research staff what would be needed to make recruitment work, including appropriate timing of events, staffing, refreshments, incentives, and taught research staff how to interact with clients.

Study personnel were trained to collect data about the number of people approached through each strategy, the number who consented and returned for pre-diabetes testing, and the number who had pre-diabetes and were enrolled in the trial. Each person would report to a welcome desk, where partners or staff captured the data on the number of people who were approached and who declined further participation before they could be screened for eligibility. At that point, staff used a computerized data management system to collect data on the flow of each person through the study. All people approached for the study received a gift afterwards. The study analyst used chi-square statistics to determine the most effective enrolment strategy and differences between those enrolled and the overall East Harlem population.

Results—In 3 months, 555 local adults were approached; 249 were appropriate candidates for further evaluation (overweight, non-pregnant, East Harlem residents without known diabetes); 179 consented and returned fasting for 1/2 day of pre-diabetes testing; and 99 had pre-diabetes and enrolled in a pilot randomized trial. The partner-led approach was most successful, recruiting 68% of people enrolled. This was also the most efficient strategy; 34% of those approached through partners were ultimately enrolled, versus 0%–17% through the other four strategies. Participants were predominantly low-income, uninsured, undereducated Spanish-speaking women.

2.4.2. Recruitment and engagement strategies approach: national workshops

The main objective of the planned national workshops within EFFICHRONIC project (WP2) is twofold:

- to identify the most important target groups of end-users – persons with (a) chronic disease(s) living under vulnerable conditions
- to elaborate a preliminary strategy to reach these groups at national level, detecting barriers and potential stakeholders for enhancing recruitment.

Within EFFICHRONIC, five workshops have been foreseen, one per country, aimed at presenting the project, obtaining relevant feedback on recruitment strategies and reaching a vast number of stakeholders and multiplier groups.

The methodology used for the elaboration of the workshops has been developed by the coordination team in Asturias. The conclusions drawn from the first workshop in Asturias served as the basis for the other national workshops and can be seen in **Annex 1**.

The national workshops are intended to inform and recruit users and different agents that can contribute to the project: health professionals, patients' organizations and public authorities.

Another objective using the workshops as a dissemination tool is to validate, modify and/or enhance the initial framework, methodologies and initially proposed approaches, as well as:

- To raise the awareness about the ambitions of EFFICHRONIC at European, national and International level, as well as its outputs and results during and after stratification.
- To inform about the project, its content, activities, progress and outputs to the target audiences and to build strategic relations and a community network even with Healthcare Institutions from countries non-involved in the consortium, reinforcing the actions of the project, getting the specific target groups to participate in the project.

The critical steps and methodologies to be taken into account when designing, planning and organising a national workshop are:

- Checklist for Identifying stakeholders and potential multipliers
- Workshop tools for priorities and sampling
- Workshop tools for recruitment
- Summarised recruitment strategy template
- Track record for sampling and recruiting
- Document on communicating with vulnerable people

SECTION 3: STANDARDS

In this section, reference is made to international standards (being: required or agreed levels of quality or attainment) that were consulted and used for the development of different parts of EFFICHRONIC, and in particular with regard to recruitment strategies.

Section 3.1 Ethical considerations

Ethics are sets of regulations or standards against which behaviours can be measured. According to the Belmont Report (The National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1979), three principles are the foundations for the protection of human research subjects: respect for persons and their autonomy, beneficence, and justice⁵¹.

To make sure internationally accepted standards were followed in EFFICHRONIC, the WHO template for the participant information letter and informed consent ⁵² has been used as an example to elaborate the informed consent. In the same way, the WHO standards on project protocols for submission to the ethics committees were consulted. This part is further described in section 4: Results and the corresponding documents can be found in annex 2.

Because of the specific design and approach of EFFICHRONIC, several additional ethical considerations have been taken into account with regard to sampling and recruitment strategies.

To start, community-based interventions must also consider the rights and wellbeing of communities and might require additional ethical considerations. According to a systematic review conducted in 2013 however, the principles involved in conducting ethical interventions are largely the same as the principles of the interventions themselves: close collaboration, trust, mutuality, shared power and decision-making and joint data ownership amongst others⁵³.

Furthermore, when addressing vulnerable populations, a particular ethical contemplation must be made. It is not regarded as ethical to merely conduct descriptive research on marginalised, disenfranchised, and vulnerable subjects and not conduct specific interventions afterwards.⁵⁴ EFFICHRONIC respects this principle by providing the study population with the benefit of the intervention, being consistent with the principle of social justice and the ethics of working with marginalized groups.

And finally, gender-issues are risks factors that must be considered in all interventions that aim at tackling the prevention and administrative response to chronic conditions in a cross-sectional and multi stakeholders approach. It is important to screen risk groups, the early detection and the enhancement of diagnostic services in terms of the promotion of gender-based approach⁵⁵. Furthermore, several studies have demonstrated how chronic disease differs among different groups of women and how it must be understood through a gender

⁵¹ Edward F. Gabrielle. (2003). *The Belmont Ethos: The Meaning of the Belmont Principles for Human Subject Protections*. *Journal of Research Administration*, 34(2), 19–24.

⁵² http://www.who.int/ethics/review-committee/informed_consent/en/

⁵³ Mikesell, L., Bromley, E., & Khodyakov, D. (2013). *Ethical community-engaged research: a literature review*. *American Journal of Public Health*, 103(12), e14. <https://doi.org/10.2105/AJPH.2013.301605>

⁵⁴ Mosavel, M., & Simon, C. (2010). *Exploratory Health Disparities Research: The Need to Provide a Tangible Benefit to Vulnerable Respondents*. *Ethics & Behavior*, 20(1), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10508420903275242>

⁵⁵ REFLECTION PROCESS on CHRONIC DISEASES - Interim Report
http://ec.europa.eu/health/major_chronic_diseases/docs/reflection_process_cd_en.pdf

approach. European men tend to assess their health status more positively than women: 70,7% perceive their health as Good or Very Good, while women report less positively on their health. This might be as a result of various factors, such as longer life expectancy of women among others⁵⁶.

Section 3.2 Multidimensional Prognostic Index (MPI)

As a stratification tool for the target population of EFFICHRONIC, the new EFFICHRONIC-oriented selfy-MPI will be used. The development and content of this tool is described in Deliverable 4.1.

The tool is based on the Multidimensional Prognostic Index (MPI), an internationally validated and standardized prognostic tool which was originally developed to define the severity grade of mortality risk in geriatric patients with chronic conditions. It includes information on clinical, cognitive, functional and nutritional aspects, as well as comorbidity, medications, and cohabitation. For EFFICHRONIC, the MPI has been adjusted to be used in a younger population, to allow self-administration and to include socio-economic information by means of the socio-familial Gijón scale. The new selfy-MPI will be tested in our target population as a stratification instrument and the EFFICHRONIC project will support the validation of the newly developed tool.

Section 3.3 Recruitment standards in vulnerable populations

As little has been published regarding this subject, no existing standards could have been consulted for the development of the project. Moreover, one of the aims of EFFICHRONIC is to develop specific recruitment standards, which will be elaborated in WP7: Guidelines & Policy Recommendations. Previously to the elaboration of these guidelines and recommendations, a compilation of experiences and best practices along the EU Member States will be implemented. Also, several patient associations and people living in socio-economically disadvantaged conditions will be consulted to collect accurate information, ensuring a well-balanced adequacy between the different cultures that coexist along the European context and the Public Health proposals and plans. The country-specific contexts will be analysed and be taken into account in order to make the policy guidelines transferable and applicable. A consensus based procedure will be applied for the elaboration of the guidelines. Furthermore, a comprehensive dissemination strategy will be implemented to engage relevant stakeholders.

⁵⁶ 37 INE (Instituto Nacional de Estadística, Spain) - Mujeres y hombres en España / Salud (actualizado 20 mayo 2015) / 4.3 Estado de salud (estado de salud percibido, enfermedades crónicas, calidad de vida, dependencia funcional)
http://www.ine.es/ss/Satellite?L=es_ES&c=INESeccion_C&cid=1259926692949&p=1254735110672&pagename=ProductosYServicios%2FPYSLayout

SECTION 4: RESULTS

Section 4.1. Ethics

Several documents have been elaborated for the correct and scientific development of the project regarding the ethical considerations of the same.

A specific participant information letter and informed consent for EFFICHRONIC is described in Annex 2. A model of the participant information letter and informed consent are attached. This model will be translated in the languages of all participating study sites and adapted to their peculiarities.

The elaboration of protocols for submission to the respective ethics committees has been an additional task in the project and they had to be developed for this specific purpose. International standards were followed as described in section 3. The approval from the corresponding Ethics committees was obtained on January 31st 2017 in Asturias and on March 27th 2018 in Genoa. In Montpellier, it was submitted on April 24th 2018 and it will be discussed on June 18th 2018.

Section 4.2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

To define the characteristics that the prospective participants must have if they are to be included in the study, and those that disqualify people from inclusion in the study, inclusion and exclusion criteria have been created. It should be noted that these criteria can vary according to the different vulnerable groups or individuals in the different implementation settings of the study.

Several aspects were taken into account when designing the criteria. For example, individuals that are vulnerable due to physical and psychological aspects (such as fragile old people, with certain disabilities or with mental health problems) may not be able to participate due to mobility issues or learning difficulties. EFFICHRONIC will consider, when targeting elderly people, to focus on those that are (i) able to come to the workshop, (ii) able to stay for the 2 and a half hours that the workshop lasts; and (iii) with sufficient cognitive ability as to understand the logic, purpose and dynamics of the training. Furthermore, individuals and groups that are vulnerable due to their socio-economic status or social exclusion situation might be subject to other limitations. As mentioned above, people sleeping on the street every night might not be suitable to join EFFICHRONIC. In the case of immigrants and foreigners, a good command of the national language is needed.

Finally, the following criteria were determined:

INCLUSION CRITERIA

Situation 1: Isolated Caregivers

- Caregiver: a person that takes care of someone with an illness. Caregivers don't have to suffer from a chronic disease, but they must have a vulnerability condition to be selected for EFFICHRONIC.
- Vulnerability condition of isolation, such as (but not only):
 - ✓ without means of transport or limited access to it
 - ✓ no Internet access
 - ✓ no or limited social support

Situation 2: Vulnerable people with a chronic disease

- A chronic disease (self-reported or clinically evaluated by medical staff) according to the International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC-2):
A chronic pathology with code between 70 and 99 registered in one of the 17 chapters, AND more than six months of evolution.
- Vulnerability condition, such as (but not only):
 - ✓ Elderly people (>65 years old) living alone or in a nursing home
 - ✓ Prisoners
 - ✓ Ethnic minorities on a low income*
 - ✓ Legal immigrants on a low income*
 - ✓ Other vulnerable persons on a low income* even if not included in the previous target groups.

*Low income: difficulties to make ends meet

EXCLUSION CRITERIA

- Age < 18.
- People living a period of crisis (domestic violence, refugees without a stable environment, eviction ...).
- Basic housing needs not met (homeless or roofless).
- Diagnosed with severe mental health problems (DSM V) (e.g. psychosis...) with distorted perception of reality and/or inability to function in a group.
- Cognitive decline (e.g. Alzheimer's), identified as a score from 43 to 50 on the "Test Your Memory" test.
- Active addictive disorders (drugs, alcohol).
- People without an adequate knowledge of the language of the country of residence.

Section 4.3. Recruitment methods based on population parameters

Using the methodology described in section 2.3, vulnerability maps have been elaborated for 3 of the 5 participating regions to identify those areas where mayor efforts should be performed to recruit target population. As mentioned before, existing data and maps have been used in the UK and in The Netherlands, it was not necessary to design specific maps.

4.3.1. Asturias, Spain

The region of Asturias is on the northern coast of Spain and has a total surface of 10.604 Km². It has a total population of 1.030.055 inhabitants.

The region of Asturias

To be able to determine vulnerability in the rural areas of Asturias, a specific index was designed as described before. In figure 5, the vulnerability map of Asturias can be appreciated. The higher the index (bright pink), the more vulnerable a region is.

Figure 5: Vulnerability in the region of Asturias according to the EFFICHRONIC index

Big municipalities: Oviedo, Gijón, y Avilés

More than half of the population (54%) lives in the 3 biggest municipalities of the region: Gijón, Avilés and Oviedo. The MEDEA index was used for these cities to design the vulnerability maps.

The following figures illustrate the different vulnerable areas of these cities. The higher the score, the more vulnerable an area is.

Figure 2: Vulnerability in Oviedo according to the MEDEA index

Figure 3: Vulnerability in Gijón according to the MEDEA index

Figure 4: Vulnerability in Avilés according to the MEDEA index

4.3.2. Department of Hérault, France

Hérault is a French department of the Region of Occitania with 1,107,398 inhabitants (year 2014) and a population density of 181.5 inhabitants per km². It has 343 municipalities of which 241 (70.3%) have less than 2,000 inhabitants and 333 (97.1%) have less than 10,000 inhabitants (rural or quasi-rural). Only Montpellier has the category of urban municipality.

FDep index of the region per municipality

In figure 6, the differences in vulnerability can be seen in the region of Hérault, France. The areas with the lowest index (bright pink) are the most vulnerable ones.

Figure 6: Vulnerability in the Hérault region according to the FDep index.

Vulnerable areas of Montpellier

In Montpellier, the Fdep index was calculated at the level of IRIS. This is illustrated in figure 7. The higher the index (bright pink), the more vulnerable are the people living in the corresponding area.

Figure 7: Vulnerability map of the city of Montpellier according to the FDep index

4.3.3. The region of Genoa, Italy

The whole metropolitan region of Genoa has approximately 800.000 inhabitants of which +/- 600.000 live in Genoa city.

METROPOLITAN AREA OF GENOA

In this region, the previously described Caranci index was used to define the vulnerable areas.

Figure 8: Vulnerability in the region of Genoa according to the Caranci index

CITY OF GENOA

Vulnerability in the city of Genoa was defined by means of the Crevari index. In figure 9, its distribution can be appreciated.

4.3.4. United kingdom

As mentioned before, no specific maps needed to be created for the UK within the framework of EFFICHRONIC due to the existing deprivation indices and maps. The following link leads to the interactive deprivation maps available for the whole of the UK: <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/english-indices-of-deprivation-2015>

Section 4.4 Template for workshops on recruitment strategies

In this section, the conclusions of the organization and guidance proposals for the national workshops is presented as a proper result of the deliverable for several reasons:

- The template for the organization of the workshops aims to serve as a guide to conduct an organized and structured workshop with clear recruitment objectives of the vulnerable target population and to help in the development of recruitment strategies.
- Initially, an exhaustive search of the available evidence was performed, and subsequently, the encountered methodology was analyzed. This process conducted to the elaboration of a quality framework to support expert opinions and future strategies.

The document contains several supporting templates. The first annex named “Checklist for Identifying stakeholders and potential multipliers”, aims not only to involve contacted stakeholders and attendees for direct participation in the workshops, but also to carry out a more detailed analysis of other potential collaborators that are absent but could be part of the recruitment process.

The second annex: “Tools for workshops – priorities of sampling” introduces key concepts that must be taken into account to help in the decision-making when prioritizing the sample. It is necessary to establish a sequential schedule and prioritize both the sample and the strategies based on specific criteria of each member country.

The third annex: “Tools for workshops – Recruitment” contemplates a collaborative filling table (chosen by means of a participatory technique) to analyze strengths and weaknesses of each particular recruitment strategy.

The fourth annex is called “summarized recruitment strategies template”

Annex n^o five: “Track record for sampling and recruitment” is to be used to track and systematize the analyzed and prioritized strategies in each National Workshop.

Annex six: “Communicating with vulnerable persons” carefully compiles all those aspects that must be specifically taken into account when working with the vulnerable, both in the national workshops themselves as later in the stages of dissemination and recruitment.

The document ends with a section of recruitment conclusions that includes all the above.

The coordination team of EFFICHRONIC created this document in order to be able to analyze and organize the information that will be valid for future experiences that addresses recruitment in vulnerable populations or similar ones.

For the document as a whole, see in **Annex 3**: “Methodology To perform National workshops”

Section 4.5 4 Recruitment methods based on individual parameters

After defining the geographical delimitation of the most vulnerable areas in the member countries of EFFICHRONIC (section 4.3: geographical vulnerability) the stage of individual recruitment can start.

To deploy the most efficient strategies for individual recruitment of the target population, being the disadvantaged population described in section 4.2. ‘Inclusion and exclusion criteria’, it is necessary to attend the most disadvantaged territories.

As already described in section 2.4 ‘individual recruitment strategies’, the development of these strategies has two anchoring points:

1. The consulted scientific evidence (section 2.4.1)
2. The contributions made by stakeholders and expert groups in the National Workshops (section 2.4.2)

In month 12 of the project, we finalized the definition of our recruitment strategy based on the two previous points. However, the recruitment process continues until month 24, with which the lessons learned from the months of recruitment in the territory, will be incorporated into the deliverable 7.1: “guidelines for Best Practices and Policy Recommendations” at the end of the project.

Based on the scientific evidence and stakeholders' contributions, the following seven dimensions define the project's individual recruitment strategies:

1. Geopolitical recruitment
2. Recruitment through formal structures of territorial organization
3. Transversal recruitment by healthcare professionals
4. Transversal attraction by social workers and related professionals
5. Specific recruitment institutionalized vulnerable people
6. Uptake by Non-Governmental Organizations (NGO)
7. Recruitment by civil society

4.5.1. Geopolitical recruitment

The geopolitical recruitment is carried out in each territory as a strategy with, at first instance, support from the highest political representatives of the city council (mayors). The objective is threefold: (i) to announce the project, contributing to its dissemination and communication, (ii) to assist the city council staff in the recruitment, training of the CDSMP, and helping out to complete the project questionnaires, and finally (iii) to mobilize the necessary resources for the transport and care of the most disadvantaged people in their territory, for them to be able to attend the programme.

Geopolitical recruitment must be as effective as possible. For this reason, the best strategy in each territory or municipality should be decided upon, depending on the geographical characteristics of each of them. For example, the alliance of several mayors of an area can be an effective strategy in some regions (e.g. the Oscos-Eo region in Asturias), or in bigger municipalities it is necessary to approach the city council individually, or even considering the urban areas per neighbourhood.

Each partner will carefully choose the intervention area before presenting the project to the corresponding mayors, and, especially at the beginning, will pay special attention to the disadvantaged geographic areas detected in the vulnerability maps.

Once an agreement has been reached, and with support from the respective maximum political representative, the technical staff of the city council will be contacted, either through an individual meeting or an internal organizational format (plenary session, etc.) From this moment, the function of the project coordinators will be to offer full support to the city council staff engaged in the project as they are the true protagonists and health agents in each territory. They will be the ones to energize the recruitment, establish the local workflow, coordinate the workshops etc.

As progress is made in recruitment, the need of working together with the other agents in the territory, such as health professionals, social workers, pharmacists and NGO's, will become clear and will be transmitted to the project coordination, with the goal of reaching the vulnerable population in a proactive way.

4.5.2. Recruitment through territorial organizations

Different territorial organizations exist in the various regions that coordinate social agents and health-care professionals, with the goal to improve of health-care coordination, organize integrated health actions etc. (e.g. In Asturias: territorial Social-healthcare coordination teams)

Firstly, in this part of the strategy, these structures have to be detected that on the one hand, might have a more institutional character and be regulated by law (e.g. in Asturias) and on the other, be less formal territorial structures (Councils of Health, Multi-sector Platforms, Municipal Health Schools, Local Governance Systems etc.).

Subsequently, it is necessary to contact these organizations and establish an open and participatory dialogue to agree on the manner in which EFFICHRONIC will be presented in these organizations.

These organizations have a high impact on the territory and are usually made up of expert people sensitized to the collaboration between social work and healthcare. It is a priority in EFFICHRONIC to contact existing assets in the territories, and begin to work with them. This is one of the principles of the key to success in the strategic planning of Citizen Participation projects.

And finally, in the same manner as in the other recruitment strategies, to introduce and coordinate all the key agents that are going to be involved in the recruitment in the territory.

4.5.3. Transversal recruitment by healthcare professionals

This strategy is based on the fact that the target population of EFFICHRONIC has a non-communicable (or chronic) disease, or is a carer for a person with a chronic illness.

From this perspective, the target population is in continuous contact with a team of health professionals who accompany him or her in the disease process, ranging from doctors, pharmacists, nurses, clinical assistants, physiotherapists, midwives to psychologists or dental hygienists. The strategy will not focus on a particular type of health professional, but on the contrary, will try to address this diverse group of professionals in a transversal way. The concept of transversality also contemplates the strategy that can be used throughout the recruitment process, accessing any geographical area of each partner, as well as being a strategy that will be coordinated with the other strategies to serve the same objective.

The information and advice provided by these professionals has an important impact on patients and is highly appreciated by them. To this strength, the possibility of reinforcement of the information in successive visits can be added, which clearly makes these personnel key in the recruitment of the target population.

The recruitment strategy for health professionals must be specifically adapted to each organization and should be started in the geographical vulnerable areas. Furthermore, a comprehensive, broad and extensive strategy should be put in place, so the information reaches all different health professionals and providers.

Priority will be given to community health services (Health Centers, Clinics and retirement facilities) to favour the possible association and subsequent coordination. However, interesting and innovative strategies coordinated from hospitals are also employed, due to the peculiarity of the different partners of the EFFICHRONIC project.

The agents who work collectively in the territory, such as Community Pharmacies, deserve special mention in this section. The collective approach of pharmacists is facilitated by their collegiate structure. Later, the individual pharmacist, who is as a reference for their clients, can recruit possible candidates for the program, prioritizing in the disadvantaged geographic areas. All people with chronic conditions and their cares need to collect drugs or devices that are issued exclusively by Community Pharmacies. This recruitment strategy offers the possibility to contact people who live isolated and who do not interact with other agents in the region.

This strategic line is being reinforced with material in writing and is being coordinated with the other strategies, to follow the evidence-based recommendations for recruitment efficiency which postulates simultaneous cross-sectional strategies always prioritizing the territory, the closest environment of the target population.

4.5.4 Transversal recruitment by professionals related to social work

The basic training and experience of professionals with a career in the field of social work, offers a complementary contribution to the exclusively health-related characteristics of the previous recruitment group.

First of all, the social workers or related professionals must be identified and grouped together to be able to establish the first contact. This refers to the fact that different structures and organizations employ social workers. Some belong to City Councils, and will be contacted for recruitment through the geopolitical strategy (4.4.1). Others work in health centers and institutions and are being coordinated within the healthcare agencies (4.4.2). Again others depend on specific organisms and Social Councils that will have to be contacted through their directive structures and that will have to be coordinated more specifically at an operational territorial level.

To wrap up, there are also social workers who work in specific programmes, that are strategically very valuable for EFFICHRONIC as they work with the same target population.(e.g.: caregiver programmes, programmes with isolated elderly people, programmes for immigrants, etc. ...). Some of these social workers develop their work within certain NGO's and fall under strategy 4.4.6.

Professionals related to social work are a great pillar of recruitment and dissemination. They are suggested as coordinators in the territory of the entire strategy, because of their strategic vision, knowledge, and reference role to their target population. Furthermore, they are well-known figures in the community and widely acknowledged by the population that attends to them.

4.5.5 Recruitment of persons in nursing homes and prisons

It is important to consider people living in closed institutions as part of the target population of EFFICHRONIC because of their unique characteristics of isolation and deprivation within these institutions.

Two kinds of institutions are being considered: prisons and nursing homes for the elderly. In all participating geographical areas of EFFICHRONIC, these institutions must be identified and contacted for the posterior dissemination of the project and recruitment of target population where legally allowed.

Special attention must be paid to this recruitment strategy. Participants recruited in this strategy could obtain the greatest benefits of the training program because of their delicate position between social inclusion and exclusion.

1. Nursing homes

According to way elderly care is organized in each of the participating countries, contact is made with the corresponding national or regional institutions to present the programme and its benefits for the target population. In each of the collaborating institutions a key contact person will be identified who will coordinate the planning and logistics of the workshops.

2. Prisons

To be able to provide the CDSMP programme in prisons, agreements with the respective centers will be sought. It is essential that prison officers or medical staff is trained as CDSMP leaders. The programme will be modified to adapt the proposals to the problems and limitations of the inmate population.

4.5.6 Recruitment by NGOs

Long is the history, the trajectory and the praiseworthy and enormous work prestigious and recognized NGO's undertake with people who are socioeconomic and culturally vulnerable.

Because of the long years of hard work, different NGO's have specialized in several areas and this has strengthened them in such a way that already many structured intervention programs exist, that they are organized with a very wide network of volunteers and professionals.

It is of strategic importance for EFFICHRONIC to work with them e. g. the Red Cross, Caritas or ACNUR in Asturias. Their collaboration is of great value for the project and is reflected in their presence in the Advisory Board, participation in all the National Workshops and recruitment of participants.

No ethical conflict exists for this recruitment strategy. There will be no personal data transfer from NGOs to the partners of EFFICHRONIC. The NGOs will be the intermediary agents that will contact and recruit the vulnerable population based on their files. These will not be shared.

In order to work with the contacted NGOs, we must be attentive and adapt our strategies to their structures and organizational circuits, and, as in the other recruitment strategies, let them be the community agents and referents of the coordination and recruitment of the target population.

4.5.7 Recruitment by civil society

Associations

A large amount of people living in the community are organized in very interesting structures, such as associations of Roma people, neighbours, women, elderly, etc. Often, they have suitable meeting places for the programme.

This strategy has to be coordinated with the before mentioned strategies. Associations have to be identified and contacted and specific strategies have to be applied in line with the characteristics of their structure and target audience.

Individuals

Last but not least, the recruitment strategy that can reach possible participants in an individual manner is by means of the variety of communication channels available to the project (radio, television, social networks, etc.) as described in Deliverable D2.1 “Communication resources”.

SECTION 5: CONCLUSIONS

The main conclusions of this deliverable derive from its proper nature. The union of working with exclusively vulnerable population and carers, and addressing the management of chronic non-communicable diseases, is an action that has not been previously addressed.

Five specific objectives were described at the beginning of this deliverable, that can be resumed in the following aspects: to define criteria and elaborate documents with regard to ethics and data protection; to define the inclusion and exclusion criteria, to determine the concept of 'vulnerability' from a population and individual point of view and to describe the standards used for this deliverable.

The methodology to reach these objectives includes a revision of current national and international regulations on data protection and ethical considerations, a theoretical framework for the design of vulnerability maps, an extensive bibliographic search on sampling and recruitment strategies, and the identification of international standards applicable to this study. The population and individual recruitment visions have been united, and experiences of macro-management have been integrated up to the most operational level and vice versa. This deliverable provides the ethical tools and information on population and individual recruitment strategies to successfully achieve the formulated objectives.

From this extensive research, several important results were obtained in this deliverable as described in section 4. To start, an informed consent form and participant information letter adapted to the target population, were designed. Furthermore, specific inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined, taking special care to be as inclusive as possible with regard to the vulnerability concept. Concerning vulnerability on a population level, geographical areas where recruitment strategies would be most effective. To adapt the theoretical background on recruitment to the particularities of each of the participating countries, a document was elaborated that serves as a tool to organize national workshops on recruitment strategies. And last but not least, seven recruitment dimensions were identified to reach the target population in the most efficient way possible.

The challenge of this vision worked on and addressed in this document, becomes a weakness if we look at its complexity to put it into practice, and the deployment of necessary resources to be successful in the final recruitment.

After reading this deliverable, it will become clear how it is intimately linked to the dissemination and communication strategies, to increase the desired impact and to be more efficient in capturing the vulnerable people who will benefit from the chronic diseases self-management programme.

A large gap of available evidence exists to approach the project as a whole, despite of the fact that methodologies exist for specific pathologies or vulnerable population separately. Likewise, from a strategic point of view, both on the macro-management level of health organizations or from the micromanagement of the small neighbourhood associations, specific strategies have been identified. In this document, all the aforementioned approaches together are highlighted. Furthermore, it is one of the aims of EFFICHRONIC to elaborate specific guidelines and standards to involve vulnerable population groups in recruitment for public health interventions. This will be further elaborated at the end of the project, in WP7

The key and main conclusion therefore is to understand the great variety of key recruitment agents in the territories that must be engaged in the process: health providers, social workers of different institutions, staff of

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

local health-related associations, or those working with vulnerable populations, pharmacists, NGOs, citizens with or without an associative or organizational network.

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

SECTION 6: ANNEXES

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

ANNEX 1: CONCLUSIONS OF THE NATIONAL WORKSHOP. PILOTING FOR THE CONSORTIUM

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

EFFICHRONIC. STRATEGIES FOR IDENTIFYING AND RECRUITING HARD-TO-REACH POPULATIONS

CONCLUSIONS FROM THE ASTURIAS WORKSHOP

Oviedo (Asturias) 3rd March 2017

1. INTRODUCTION

As part of the overall communication strategy in Asturias, a workshop was held on 3rd March 2017 in Oviedo to: (i) present EFFICHRONIC to the wide community of health professionals and the public; and (ii) consider and discuss different strategies for reaching out vulnerable populations with experts, stakeholders and decision-makers. While the assistance to the first part of the workshop was opened to everybody, the participation in the discussion group was subject to invitation by the EFFICHRONIC team in Asturias.

Seventeen people from Asturias and other Spanish regions took part in the workshop which lasted for over two hours. The Discussion Paper that precedes this document and which had been previously circulated to participants facilitated the discussion. The three discussion grids included in the Discussion Paper were used for the discussion. The audience contributed ideas and recommendations and assessed the feasibility as well as the pros and cons of the different strategies considered.

2. DISCUSSION ON POTENTIAL VULNERABLE GROUPS AND STRATEGIES FOR RECRUITMENT

A key conclusion that soon became clear in the workshop discussion relates to the usefulness of the definition of vulnerability suggested in the Discussion Paper and fully embraced by the workshop experts. Vulnerability is an “intermediate zone located between the zone of social integration (a stable job, solid social and family pillars) and the zone of social exclusion (jobless, social isolation, lack of family ties), thus becoming a more unstable zone, with precarious jobs, intermittent periods of employment and unemployment and with weak social and family relations” (Cruz Roja 2006). Seeing vulnerability as an “intermediate zone” helps to identify

both old and new profiles of individuals in a situation of vulnerability, ranging from the homeless and ethnic disadvantaged minorities to pensioner women or qualified young foreigners (mainly women).

The different vulnerable individuals/groups suggested by the Discussion Paper – i.e. the frail elderly, the disabled, the legal migrants, people living on benefits, prisoners- fit well within that definition of vulnerability and were considered and discussed at the workshop. But the definition of vulnerability also allowed identifying those “new” profiles of individuals and groups that, especially due to the economic crisis, have fallen into the vulnerability trap – from young professionals and their families to informal caregivers (mostly women) – and as such, these were equally discussed by the workshop experts. While the workshop participants did not undertake a prioritising exercise as such, there was however a coincidence in viewing (old) individuals living alone, women informal caregivers and the gypsy minority as the most appropriate for the Effichronic project.

Overall, the long list of potential profiles discussed included the following:

a) Individuals living alone

- Characteristics: This is a broad group of people, of both sexes, very often of old age and eventually with mental health problems. But it is not a heterogeneous group who associate and get together at certain places.
- Sources to access:
 - Key neighbourhood points:
 - Bakery (bread is a very cheap Food and elderly people consume a high quantity of cereals)
 - Parish and religious communities
 - Retail Pharmacy (local Chemist)
 - Health Centres: Primary Care Centres (General Practitioners and nurses), Hospitals, nurseries and day care centres.
 - One potential source for getting to individuals living (and feeling) alone is by approaching the users of the “Teléfono de la Esperanza” – a free phone number for people in (suicide) crisis, run by a Spanish non-for-profit organization, who provides advice, support and facilitates access to psychological and other services. This approach would require reaching an agreement with this organization.
 - Social Workers from the council (municipal) social care services
- Requirements: The CDSMP requirements seem to fit comfortably with individuals living alone.

b) Informal Caregivers (mainly women)

- Characteristics: a clear “hidden” group that suffer from excessive workload and loneliness, while on many occasions, in an adverse or non-favourable socio-economic situation. In rural areas, they may be in ever greater isolation and vulnerable position. While women are the vast majority of caregivers in Spain, some participants also suggested considering men.
- Sources to access:

- Key neighbourhood points:
 - Bakery (bread is a very cheap Food and elderly people consume a high quantity of cereals)
 - Parish and religious communities – Cáritas is a Spanish religious NGO that may be particularly helpful for the Effichronic project.
 - Retail Pharmacy (local Chemist)
- Health Centres: Primary Care Centres (General Practitioners and nurses), Hospitals, nurseries and day care centres.
- The Snowball strategy⁵⁷ is suggested as a potential way of identifying carers of other people.
- Requirements:
 - Caregivers have little time for themselves, and hence this may pose problems to take time from their caring day-to-day activity to come to CDSMP training. Replacement or other compensatory actions for allowing them to assist the seminars could be considered, including agreeing on formal care services at home during the time of the training.
 - An example from Catalonia was mentioned: CDSMP seminars for caregivers were set to coincide with memory-enhancement sessions for people with dementia, so caregivers could attend at the same time as the people they care for.
 - Sometimes, the intervention may need to be culturally adapted to the target group.

c) Prisoners

- Characteristics: both men and women.
- Sources to access: In Asturias, the regional prison centre is the CP Villabona, who has around 1.300 inmates. This will require an agreement with the Centre and ensure the training of prison officers on the CDSMP.
- Requirements:
 - Professionals working in Villabona might need between 2 and 3 months for training and leading the seminars.
 - The programme might need, also, a substantial modification to adapt the proposals to the problems and limitations of inmate population. CDSMP is based on peer-learning: the approach could include a collaborative and group-based methodology attending to the specific characteristics of those individuals who comprise the target group.
 - Inmates could want to change their lifestyle and adopt healthier routines, but being deprived of their liberty, their individual attitudes and willingness may be severely constrained. There are not any compensatory measures to overcome these limitations.

d) Legal migrants

⁵⁷Sadler, G. R., Lee, H. C., Lim, R. S. H., & Fullerton, J. (2010). Recruitment of hard-to-reach population subgroups via adaptations of the snowball sampling strategy. *Nursing & health sciences*, 12(3), 369-374.

- **Characteristics:** In Asturias there are approx.10,000 legal migrants and 2,000 estimated illegal migrants. Migrants from Romania and Ecuador represent 70% of the whole migrant population. High incidence of diabetes is observed in migrants from Pakistan.
Eritrean young men suffer from chronic conditions and drug abuse.
- **Sources to access:** Certain migrant populations such as Ecuadorians are likely to socialise among themselves, gathering specifically in public places and meeting with relatives and peers at lunchtime. Hence, these groups are easier to recruit.
The Romanian population can be approach through their schooled kids.
In Asturias, a number of organizations that work with migrants and refugee populations can support EFFICHRONIC in identifying and approaching candidates for the program:
 - Asturias Acoge <http://www.asturiasacoge.org/spip/?page=quienes-somos> is a local NGO that provides reception and promotes integration of migrant populations through training and social campaigns against xenophobia and racism.
 - ACCEMM <http://www.accem.es/en/about-us/introduction> is a Spanish non-governmental organization (NGO) that provides attention and reception to refugees and immigrants in Spain promoting its social and labour integration, as well as equal rights and duties of everyone.
 - Cruz Roja Española Asturias <http://www.cruzroja.es/principal/web/principado-de-asturias> is the Asturias section of the international movement The Red Cross.
- **Requirements:**
 - Migrants need, at least, an A2 level in Spanish language.
 - A cultural and linguistic adaptation of the CDSMP materials may be needed. For example, for Latin-American migrants, the language and its use should be adapted to their peculiarities (Latin-American Spanish). This however, shouldn't be much of a problem, as such adaptation has always been considered by the Stanford programme.

e) Romani Community

- **Characteristics:** The Romani community is the largest ethnic minority in the region: 10.000 persons in Asturias.

In terms of their socioeconomic status, gipsies can be divided into various levels: there are families with middle socio-economic level (stable housing and job, etc.) and families who trade with scrap metal, gathering or buying it, both able to make ends meet. These two levels are the most representative and are probably the most candidates to participate in CDSMP training. At the far end of the exclusion continuum, there are also gipsy individuals living in slums or segregated areas, and their social exclusion situation might not make them direct candidates to the program.

- **Sources to access:** The Romani community in Spain is represented through two main associations:
 - UNGA <http://asociaciongitanaunga.com/> is an Asturian gypsy association
 - Fundación Secretariado Gitano (Roman Community Secretariat) <https://www.gitanos.org/asturias/index.php> is a non-profit organization that provides services for the development of the Roma community in Spain and in Europe.
- **Requirements:**
 - Interaction with outsiders and non-gypsies ("payos") at the CDSMP courses could be problematic.

- A cultural and linguistic adaptation of the CDSMP materials may be needed. The experts wondered to what extent the CDSMP could be really adapted to this population.

f) Old People living in rural areas

- Characteristics: The population of Asturias is concentrated in the central metropolitan triangle formed between the cities of Avilés-Oviedo-Gijón. Of the million people that live in Asturias, 150,000 live very much dispersed in rural areas. The vast majority of them are old women who live quite isolated.
- Sources to access: These people may be religious and attend mass regularly, so their local parish may be a source to identify and register them.
 - The Rural Women Association ("Asociación de Mujeres Rurales) of Asturias could be a very interesting partner for Effichronic Asturias.
 - The workshop considered the possibility of collaborating with the post office services to access to these isolated people, but the Mail Service was not seen as particularly collaborative so the idea did not prosper.
 - It was however suggested the possibility of broadcasting adverts on the local TV and radios to reach these isolated people.
- Requirements:
 - Barriers: distance and access (e.g. some rural areas are 1 or 2 hours away from the main cities). Non-adherence due to mobility issues and lack of own transport have been reported.

f) New vulnerable families

- Characteristics: These are populations mostly affected by the ongoing economic crisis, who may have not lost family ties or social relations, but have lost their jobs and socioeconomic status. The Asturias Food Bank supports around 27,000 people every year.
- Sources to access:
 - These families may be getting help from council (municipality) care services or Food Banks (Banco de Alimentos <http://www.bancaliasturias.org/>). Both organizations could be explored as potential allies for the Effichronic project.
 - Health centres might be another point of contact with these people.
 - Schools can be a source of access. Principals, tutorship or teachers could detect situations of malnutrition or undernourishment of children.
 - Contacting associations of families could also be considered.
- Requirements:
 - In terms of CDSMP requirements, the experts at the workshop did not identify any particular element that could determine the success of the project.
 - The key problem may lie in clearly identifying who would fall into this group: which criteria should be used?

ASTURIAS TARGET GROUPS, AGREED STRATEGIES AND COLLABORATIONS

TARGET GROUP	TARGET NUMBER	AGREED STRATEGIES	SEEK COLLABORATIONS FROM
Individuals living alone	500	<p>In the geographical areas identified in Phase I of EFFICHRONIC, proceed to identify and get in touch with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bakeries • Parishes (and parish Caritas) • Retail Pharmacy (local Chemist) • Health Centres: Primary Care Centres (General Practitioners and nurses), Hospitals, nurseries and day care centres. <p>*To consider: "Teléfono de la Esperanza"</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local Retail Pharmacy Association (Colegio Oficial Farmacéuticos Asturias, COF) • Each Retail Pharmacy of the selected neighbourhood • "Párrocos" (parish priest) + Caritas parroquial • Caritas Asturias • Primary Care District Managers • Health Centre District Managers • Primary Care centre GPs and nurses • Day centres ("Centros de día")
Informal Caregivers	500	<p>In the geographical areas identified in Phase I of EFFICHRONIC, proceed to identify and get in touch with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bakeries • Parishes (and parish Caritas) • Retail Pharmacy (local Chemist) • Health Centres: Primary Care Centres (General Practitioners and nurses), Hospitals, nurseries and day care centres. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local Retail Pharmacy Association (Colegio Oficial Farmacéuticos Asturias, COF) • Each Retail Pharmacy of the selected neighbourhood • "Párrocos" (parish priest) + Caritas parroquial • Caritas Asturias • Primary Care District Managers • Health Centre District Managers • Primary Care centre GPs and nurses
Prisoners	100	Identification and selection at the Villabona Prison	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Villabona Prison Director and management
Legal migrants	200	Decide whether to access through any (or all) of the three organizations suggested – Asturias Acoge, ACCEMM or Cruz Roja Española Asturias	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decide accordingly which organization to approach
Gypsy minority	200	Decide whether to access through the suggested organizations and which one should this be – UNGAS or Fundación Secretariado Gitano	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decide accordingly which organization to approach
Old People living in rural areas	300	<p>Approach through the Local Councils (ayuntamientos). The Rural Women Association could be a key partner.</p> <p>*To consider: broadcasting adverts on the local TV and radios</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ayuntamientos • Rural Women Association
New vulnerable families	25	<p>Council (municipality) care services or Food Banks</p> <p>*To consider: schools of the pre-selected areas</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Caritas • Banco de Alimentos Asturias

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

ANNEX 2: PARTICIPANTS' INFORMATION SHEET AND CERTIFICATE OF CONSENT FOR PARTICIPATION IN THE RESEARCH STUDY: EFFICHRONIC.

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

PARTICIPANTS' INFORMATION SHEET

TITLE OF THE STUDY: *EFFICHRONIC: Analysis of the efficiency of a chronic disease self-management program in socioeconomic vulnerable population in five European countries.*

MAIN INVESTIGATOR:

CENTER:

This document aims to provide you with information about a research study in which you are invited to participate. This study was approved by the [Research Ethics Committee of](#)

.....

If you choose to participate in it, you should receive personalized information from the researcher, **read this document beforehand** and be able to ask all questions you need to understand the details of the study. If you wish, you can take the document with you and consult it with other people. You can take the time necessary to decide whether to participate or not.

Participation in this study is completely **voluntary**. You can decide not to participate or, if you agree to do so, change your mind by withdrawing the consent at any time without giving explanations. We assure you that this decision will not affect the health care to which you are entitled.

What is the purpose of the study?

The main objective of EFFICHRONIC is to demonstrate the usefulness of a self-management program in people with chronic diseases or their carers, especially in the more disadvantaged population groups. It will be implemented in five European countries and will last for three years. [In Asturias, it will be carried out within the framework of the existing program "Active Patient Asturias".](#)

Why am I being offered the opportunity to participate?

You are invited to participate because you have a chronic illness and belong to a population group with certain social, economic or geographical characteristics, or you take care of someone with a chronic illness and you are in a somewhat isolated situation, due to lack of means of transportation, not having internet at home or not having close social support.

What does my participation consist of?

People who want to participate in the study will be asked to complete three questionnaires: two before starting the programme and one 6 months after the programme has finished. The latter will be sent by mail, by email or hand delivered according to your preference. You will receive the initial questionnaires along with this information letter or at the beginning of the first workshop. The first questionnaire covers clinical data, activities of daily living, medication, memory test and socioeconomic data. The second questionnaire is about your state of health, lifestyle, etc. You can fill in the

questionnaires with the help of a relative or carer. It is very important to contact the researcher if you do not want to receive the third questionnaire or if your contact information has changed.

Will participating in the study cause me any inconvenience or discomfort?

The only disadvantage of participating in the study is the time needed to complete the questionnaires. It will take approximately one hour to complete the 3 questionnaires, between 20 and 30 minutes per questionnaire. Your participation will not cause any additional inconveniences.

Will I receive any benefit?

You are not expected to get any direct benefit for participating in the study. This research aims to discover unclear aspects about the management of chronic diseases in different population groups. This information may be useful for other people in the future.

Will I receive the information obtained from the study?

If you wish, you will be given a summary of the study results.

Will the results of this study be published?

The study results will be sent to scientific journals for dissemination, but no data will be transmitted that could lead to the identification of the participants.

How will the confidentiality of my data be protected?

Data processing, communication and transfer will be done in accordance with the provisions of [\(national regulation\)](#) and, as of May 25, 2018, in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation, the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.

At any time, you can exercise your data protection rights (opposition, access, rectification, deletion, limitation or portability), unless you are the subject of a decision based solely on the automated processing of your data and the revocation of the consent given. To do so, you must contact the [Citizen Assistance Service of](#)([address](#) - [telephone](#) - [email](#)).

Only the research team and the health authorities ([if applicable](#)), who have the duty to maintain confidentiality, will have access to all collected study data. Only information that cannot be identified may be transmitted to third parties. In the event of information transmission to other countries, it will be carried out anonymously with a data protection level according to the Regulation (EU) 2016/679.

Your data will be collected and preserved until the study is finished in a codified way, which means that they have a code with which the research team can know who they belong to.

The person responsible for data custody is responsible for the data file and treatment. At the end of the study, the data will be anonymized.

Are there economic interests in this study?

This research is promoted by [\(Organization\)](#) with funds provided by the Health Programme of the European Union (2014-2020) as part of the joint project / action '738127 / EFFICHRONIC'.

The principal investigator will not receive specific retribution for the dedication to the study. You will not be paid for participating in it.

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

How to contact the research team of this study?

You can contact (names) at (phone number) or (email)

For more information, see the study website: [www.http://effichronic.eu/](http://effichronic.eu/)

Thank you very much for your help!

Signature of participant:

Signature of investigator:

Name and surname:

Name and surname:

.....

.....

Date: .../.../20...

Date: .../.../20...

CERTIFICATE OF CONSENT FOR PARTICIPATION IN THE RESEARCH STUDY: EFFICHRONIC.

I,.....

- read the participant information sheet of the above mentioned study that was given to me, and I was able to ask all the questions about the study.

- understand that my participation is voluntary, and that I can withdraw from the study whenever I want, without having to give explanations and without this having an impact on my medical care.

- agree to the use of my data in the conditions detailed in the participant information sheet.

- freely give my consent to participate in this study.

Address:

Municipality: Postcode.....

Email:.....

Phone number:

Signature of participant:

Signature of investigator:

Name and surname:

Name and surname:

.....

.....

Date: .../.../20...

Date: .../.../20...

Please, leave blank

Participant number:

Two forms must be signed: one for the participant, one for the investigator

CERTIFICATE OF WITNESSED CONSENT FOR PARTICIPATION IN THE RESEARCH STUDY EFFICHRONIC (in case the participant cannot read or write)

The impartial witness must be a person from outside the investigation team.

I,, as an impartial witness, affirm that in my presence:

- the participant information sheet of the aforementioned study that was given to me, and was read to, and he/she was able to ask all the questions about the study.
- He/she understood that his/her participation is voluntary, and that he/she can withdraw from the study at any time, without having to give explanations and without this having an impact on his/her medical care.
- He/she gives access to the use of his/her data in the conditions detailed in the participant information sheet.
- he/she freely gives his/her consent to participate in this study.

Address:

Municipality: Postcode.....

Email:.....

Phone number:

Signature of witness:

Signature of investigator:

Name and surname:

Name and surname:

.....

.....

Date: .../.../20...

Date: .../.../20...

Please, leave blank

Participant number:

Two forms must be signed: one for the participant, one for the investigator

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

ANNEX 3: METHODOLOGY TO PERFORM NATIONAL WORKSHOPS

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

EFFICHRONIC

BASIC METHODOLOGY TO PERFORM NATIONAL WORKSHOPS TO DEFINE RECRUITMENT STRATEGIES FOR VULNERABLE GROUPS

RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS OF SPANISH WORKSHOP IN ASTURIAS

Content

Introduction.....	61
Methodology.....	63
Promotion and Communication campaign	63
Invitations monitoring.....	64
Participation management	64
Preparation materials.....	64
Discussion groups	64
Post-event summaries and feedback gathering.....	64
Literature review	65
Conclusions – Asturias	66
Priorities and Targets.....	66
Inclusion and exclusion criteria for Asturias were agreed as follows:	69
NATIONAL WORKSHOPS IN EFFICHRONIC	70
ANNEX 1 - Check list for Identifying stakeholders and potential multipliers	0
ANNEX 2 - Tools for workshops – priorities and sampling	1
ANNEX 3 – Tools for workshops - Recruitment.....	2
ANNEX 4 - Summarised recruitment strategy template	3
ANNEX 5 - Track record for sampling and recruiting.....	4
ANNEX 6 - Communicating with vulnerable persons	5
ANNEX 7 – Conclusions paper	6

INTRODUCTION

The main objective of the national workshops planned and defined within EFFICHRONIC project (WP2) is twofold:

- to identify the most important **target groups of end-users** – persons with chronic disease/s living under vulnerable conditions
- to elaborate a preliminary strategy for reaching these groups **at the national level**, detecting **barriers and potential stakeholders for enhancing the recruitment processes**.

The first workshop of this series was carried out in Spain, Asturias. This report summarises the methodology and tools used for the organization and implementation of the mentioned first workshop, together with the conclusions and results obtained. The purpose is to provide knowledge and instruments to be transferred and scaled up in the other countries involved in the project to engage relevant stakeholders and key multipliers to ensure appropriate recruitment strategies.

The workshop in Spain, Asturias was held on March of 2017, but the preparative work started on February 2017 and the conclusions elaboration ended in June 2017. The main objectives of the workshop were

1. **To define, identify and prioritise the most important targeted populations in Asturias according to EFFICHRONIC requirements.**
2. **To identify barriers and seek for new paths, methods and multiplier groups in order to optimise an effective communication to ensure recruitment**
3. **To determine inclusion and exclusion criteria of the identified populations.**

The entities SESPA/CSPA and FICYT implemented the workshop. In order to reach the target public, the entities (1) identified within the target experts to be involved in the workshops; (2) categorised the experts regarding profile, access to specific vulnerable groups, or expertise; (3) invited them, also sending the preparation materials detailed below.

The workshop was characterised for its complementary perspectives and technical/practical approaches and expertise (e.g., from civil society – e.g., Cruz Roja, etc. -, public administration and Health services or academic institutions). In general, the group was comprised by the following profiles:

- **Civil Society** representatives (mainly, the NGO *Cruz Roja de España*, part of the Red Cross International, and also the Association of Women Living in Rural Areas of Asturias, association of Cardiovascular disorder patients, Save the Children)

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

- Representatives from **National Health System and regional or local Public Administrations** relevant in Public health issues (e.g. Ministerio de Sanidad y Consumo de España, Red de Escuelas de Salud para la Ciudadanía, Municipalities or local corporations, etc)

The following sections describe a) the methodology used to successfully implement the workshop carried out in Asturias which will be the basis for the design of other 4 national workshops; b) the results and conclusions achieved in Spain concerning the recruitment strategy of vulnerable populations.

METHODOLOGY

The present section includes the main results and findings achieved through an in-depth analysis of the implemented workshop in Asturias. The Workshop followed a series of processes for obtaining information and reporting data; in particular:

- Promotion and communication campaign about the workshop to engage relevant stakeholders
- Invitations monitoring
- Participation management
- Preparation of materials
- Discussion group dynamics
- Post-event summaries and feedback gathering
- Literature review

Promotion and Communication campaign

The workshop was promoted, at least, two months in advance. During this preparatory stage, the Project Coordinator organised the main activities to improve the dissemination of the event. These could include:

- Direct communication: each partner involved (SESPA, CSPA and FICYT) communicated directly with local press representatives, health and social professionals who may be interested, public administration representatives and any other stakeholder identified.
- Newspapers: Mass media was a valuable resource regarding society and, most important, key associations, NGOs and end-users (patients with chronic diseases). Regional and local newspapers are a crucial dissemination and communication resource concerning civil society and end-users.

Table 1 - Ideas for Promoting a National Workshop

Audience	Potential method/s to be used	Reason/s
Public administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct communication, at local level - Press releases, interviews (newspapers) - Event announced on the SESPA, CSPA and FICYT's websites - Social Media (SESPA, CSPA, FICYT) 	<p>The Internet and social media are widely used by the European citizenship and civil society. Mass media and press releases need a more balanced direct approach. The direct communication with stakeholders seems to be a very efficient and engaging way for increasing the workshops attendance at medium-term.</p>
Civil Society	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Direct engagement → Direct communication at local level - Website and Social Media 	<p>SESPA/CSPA and FICYT will liaise with Associations and NGOs, but also with social workers and any other potential multiplier target group, for contributing to reach the most extensive impact regarding end-users, relatives and informal caregivers.</p>
All target groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Press articles/releases 	<p>SESPA/CSPA and FICYT are public entities, so they have an excellent opportunity for building a well-established collaborative relationship with local media (newspapers, televisions, independent journalists, etc.).</p>

Invitations monitoring

An essential task is to identify prior entities that must be involved in the workshop. More than 20 members attended the workshop, being **Associations** (e.g., Mujeres Rurales de Asturias), **NGOs** (e.g., Cruz Roja de España) and **Public Administration** – specifically, social work and health professionals - represented within the group.

Participants were selected according to their activity in **specific populations** (e.g. chronic patients, marginal groups), their **knowledge about the CDSMP** and/or their **experience recruiting hard-to-reach and vulnerable people**.

Then, the Project Coordinator compiled a list of emails and contact means for sending the invitations and the preparatory document. Direct invitations were made by SEPSA/CSPA - via email or the most convenient media to its own contacts and the prioritized Spanish stakeholders and experts. [Check ANNEX 1 for more information](#)

Participation management

PhD. Marta Pisano (SESPA), registered the confirmations and disconfirmations and supported interested participants answering to their questions, doubts and requirements. A list of participants was elaborated by SESPA/CSPA.

Preparation materials

Materials were prepared to be read by the attendees ([ANNEX 2](#) and [ANNEX 3](#)) to better contribute to the workshop discussions were elaborated in the participants' mother tongue (Spanish). Considering as a basis the EFFICHRONIC proposal and the indicators specified therein, SEPSA and FICYT prepared the materials that were sent to all participants **3 weeks in advance**. **In addition, attendees received some templates to be filled with specific information**. They elaborated on the required model and contributed with new alternatives, scales and suggestions for improvement within the original dimensions considered.

Discussion groups

By implementing focus groups, the attendees defined the key targeted populations to be part of the recruitment process in EFFICHRONIC. An initial proposal was redefined or validated, prioritising end-users and analysing the different existing stakeholders or potential multiplier groups/individuals to be used. As a result, a preliminary recruitment strategy for Asturias was elucidated. [See Priorities and Targets for more information](#).

Post-event summaries and feedback gathering

The discussion groups were recorded, and the transcriptions summarised; the transcriptions provided the material to develop the analysis on the perception and conclusions of the participating entities, coming from all over Spain (Asturias, Balearic Islands, Andalusia, Catalonia, etc.). The summary was sent to involved participants in order to obtain additional feedback or clarifications. [See ANNEX 4 for a template](#)

Literature review

The workshop's conclusions were cross-referenced and, afterwards, completed with additional literature. An elaborated document was issued in April compiling most of the conclusions (ANNEX 7). Additionally, the results were discussed in Luxembourg, where the Spanish methodology and results were presented as an initial recruitment framework, which was aligned with the dissemination strategy as shown in *D2.1. – Dissemination materials – Sections 2 and 7 (Target groups and Communication for enhancing the recruitment strategy, respectively)*

CONCLUSIONS – ASTURIAS

Priorities and Targets

The *vulnerability* was defined by participants as an intermediate condition between “social integration” and “social exclusion”. *Vulnerability* refers to both, the social dimension and the personal dimension of a certain individual. The vulnerability must be evaluated in relation to different socio-economic and socio-cultural indicators: sex, age, living conditions, credentials and qualification, etc.

The identified groups (Activity 1) were:

Table 2 - Activity 1: Discussion about the designated end-users target groups

GROUP	CONTEXT	CIVIL SOCIETY PLAYERS	RECRUITMENT STRATEGY	GROUP vs CDSMP
WOMEN – INFORMAL CAREGIVERS	Excessive workload, discomfort, adverse or non-favourable socio-economic conditions, economic dependence. Target: Low socioeconomic status, rural areas. Some participants suggest also include men	None	Snowball strategy ⁵⁸	Problems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Leisure time is not enough - Sometimes, the intervention must be culturally adapted to the target group - Gender Roles Potential solutions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compensatory services for reducing the care workload (day-care centres, seminars aimed at cared people...)
INDIVIDUALS LIVING ALONE	Both sexes Sometimes, these might have mental disorders	“Teléfono de la Esperanza” (Spanish NGO working on suicide prevention)	General practitioners Nurseries and day-care centres	CDSMP fits this group's requirements
Roman community	Roman community is the majority ethnic minority in the region: 10.000 persons in Asturias, an area with a very low immigration rate (migrants only represent 12.000 individuals) Currently, these persons are stratified into 5 levels: the 1 st level is comprised of families with middle socio-economic level (stable housing and job, etc.). The 2 nd level represents a gap: these families trade with scrap metal, gathering or buying it. These two levels are the most representative. The 5 th group of individuals live in	Groups 1 and 2 are more accessible. Groups 4 (inmates) and 5 (slums) are not vulnerable: instead, are grouped in a social exclusion situation.	Two associations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - UNGA - Secretariado Gitano 	Can the CDSMP be adapted to this population? Could we slightly modify the toolkit for adapting it? The Asturian Roman community is the population most needed to intervention in the field of Health and empowerment, but also the most complex to recruit.

⁵⁸Sadler, G. R., Lee, H. C., Lim, R. S. H., & Fullerton, J. (2010). Recruitment of hard-to-reach population subgroups via adaptations of the snowball sampling strategy. *Nursing & health sciences*, 12(3), 369-374.

	slums or segregated areas.			
INMATES – MEN AND WOMEN		CP Villabona (Regional prison and detention centre)	Professionals working in Villabona might need between 2 and 3 months for training and leading the seminars. The programme might need, also, a substantial modification to adapt the proposals to the problems and limitations of the inmate population. - CDSMP is based on peer-learning: the approach could include a collaborative and group-based methodology attending to the specific characteristics of those individuals who comprise the target group. Inmates could want to change their lifestyle and adopt healthier routines, but being deprived of their liberty, their individual attitudes and willingness are severely constrained. There are not any compensatory measures to overcome these constrictions.	
MIGRANTS - MEN AND WOMEN	In Asturias, there are approx. 10000 legal migrants and 2000 estimated illegal migrants. Migrants from Romania and Ecuador represent 70% of them. High incidence of diabetes observed in migrants from Pakistan. Eritrean young men: chronic conditions and drug abuse observed.	Ecuadorians are likely to socialise, specifically, in public places. They usually meet with relatives and peers at lunchtime. Are easier to recruit and enjoy a good social inclusion Social workers identify the Romanian population monitoring the schooled kids	ACCEM Asturias Acoge Cruz Roja	Illegal migrants do not Access to the National Health System: so, their situation is not vulnerable, is social exclusion. Cultural and linguistic adaptation Migrants need, at least, an A2 in Spanish. Latin-American migrants: the language and its use should be adapted to their peculiarities (Latin-American Spanish) – However, it has been considered by the Stanford programme since the beginning.

As regards Activity 2, main multipliers groups were identified:

1. Health Centres
2. Bakery (bread is a very cheap food and elderly people consume a high quantity of cereals)
3. Parish and religious communities
4. Drugstore

Groups, strategies and barriers are summarised in the table below, elaborated through brainstorming

Table 3 - Activity 1: Identification of Strategies and Multipliers (seeds)

GROUP	STRATEGIES, COMMENTS
New vulnerable populations (general population affected by the crisis)	Municipality services Food Banks Paediatricians Health Centres NGOs → these persons are not associated with NGOs, but they ask for support, Food (27000 individuals

	<p>in Asturias, 2016), etc. Schools and high-schools – principals, tutorship or teachers could detect situations of malnutrition or undernourishment. Associations of Families should also be considered.</p>
Roman community	<p>Interaction with outsiders (“payos”) could be problematic. SESPA should work with the associations above.</p>
Informal caregivers	<p>Main challenge: replacement or other compensatory actions for allowing them to assist the seminars. Previously validated in Catalonia: re-organization of the seminars (match with a memory-enhancement programme for people with dementia) Municipality services: formal caregiving at home (certain days) Drugstore, parish (e.g., Caritas is a parish-based NGO)</p>
Rural community	<p>150000 are living in rural areas. The vast majority of them are women living isolated. These tend to be religious and enrolled in parishes and religious communities. Barriers: distance and access (e.g. some rural areas are 1 hour or 2hours far away from the main city) Non-adherence due to mobility issues and lack of own transport have been reported.</p> <p>Recruitment: “<i>Date un respiro</i>” (replacement of caregivers programme), “<i>Consejo de la Mujer</i>”, TV shows and interviews. Postmen/women are not an adequate option</p>
Individuals living alone	<p>How to identify them</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Social Workers -NHS card -Municipality -In-home formal caregiving -NGOs (Help hotline/<i>Teléfono de la Esperanza</i>) <p>Sampling based on specific sites and schedules frequently used for recruiting socially excluded people could work on these settings too (accordingly to the research, <i>Time-Location Sampling Techniques</i> worked for homeless people, drug abusers, high-risk groups due to specific sexual practices such as cruising or sex work)</p> <p>Problem: the sampling should be more precise than the others specified above. New questions should be defined (e.g., have you ever thought to ask for benefits?) -- The “<i>Escala Gijón/Gijón Scale</i>” can be used)</p>

Inclusion and exclusion criteria for Asturias were agreed as follows:

Inclusion criteria

Case 1 - Isolated Caregivers

- Caregivers: people who take care of a sick person. Caregivers don't have to suffer from a chronic disease, but they must have a vulnerability condition to be selected in EFFICHRONIC.
- Isolated (vulnerability condition):
 - people who do not have transport or limited transport
 - no Internet access

Case 2 - People presenting the following two conditions:

- **Chronic disease** (self-reported or clinically evaluated by the medical staff): According to the International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC-2), patients with chronic pathology will be those who have a disease registered in any of the 17 chapters, with code between 70 and 99 and have more than six months of evolution.
- **Vulnerability condition, such as (but not only)**
 - Elderly people (65-80 years old) living alone
 - Inmates
 - Ethnic minority with low income
 - Legal Migrants with low income
 - New vulnerable with low income

Exclusion criteria

- Period of **crisis** (domestic violence, refugees, repossession of home)
- **Basic housing needs not met** (homeless or roofless)
- Diagnosed severe mental health disorder/s only if **the mental disorder could undermine** the subjects' functionality and the **accomplishment of the objectives pursued by the CDSMP** (e.g., a patient during an episode of mental suffering, psychosis, etc., making impossible to follow the programme, initiating and maintaining lifestyle changes, etc.)
- **Cognitive decline** (e.g. Alzheimer's) Identified as 3 or more errors in the Pfeiffer Spanish version (when people know how to read and write, and 4 or more for those who do not).
- **Drug and alcohol addiction**
- Those without adequate level of **language** of the country of residence

In sum,

- **Caregivers:** these are people who take care of a sick person, excluding children. As you can see on the table, caregivers do not have to suffer from a chronic disease, but they must have a vulnerability condition to be selected in EFFICHRONIC.
- **New vulnerable people:** It is the person that, even not included in the other target groups, has the following vulnerable condition: chronic disease and low income.
- **Low income:** when the person does not reach the minimum inter-professional salary in their country

- **Low level of education:** According to the international standard classification of education (ISCED), these are people who do not have studies, or primary studies (level 1).
- **Chronic disease:** on average any disease lasting more than six months may be considered chronic. According to the International Classification of Primary Care (CIAP), patients with chronic pathology will be those who have a disease registered in any of the 17 chapters, with code between 70 and 99 and have more than six months of evolution.

NATIONAL WORKSHOPS IN EFFICHRONIC

As said, within EFFICHRONIC, five workshops were foreseen, **aimed to present the project, obtaining relevant feedback on strategies to support sample recruitment and reaching a vast number of stakeholders and multiplier groups.**

Four national workshops are still to be organised in France, the Netherlands, Italy and the United Kingdom for designing a well-founded and a scoped set of recruitment strategies adapted to each national context and cultural background. Thus, the **national workshop is intended to inform and recruit users and different agents** that contribute to the project: health professionals, patients' organizations and public authorities.

Another objective linked with the workshops as dissemination channels is to **validate, modify and/or enhance the initial framework, methodologies and approaches initially proposed**, as well as:

- To raise the awareness at European, national and International level about the EFFICHRONIC ambitions, the outputs and results **during and after the stratification**
- To **inform about the project**, its content, activities, progress and outputs to the target audiences and to build **strategic relations and a networked** community even with Healthcare Institutions from countries non-involved in the consortium, reinforcing **the actions of the project**, getting the specific target groups to participate in the project.

Annexes enclosed to this document summarise the methodologies and critical steps to be taken into account when designing, planning and organising national workshops:

- **ANNEX 1 - Checklist for Identifying stakeholders and potential multipliers**
- **ANNEX 2 - Tools for workshops – priorities and sampling**
- **ANNEX 3 – Tools for workshops - Recruitment**

- **ANNEX 4 - Summarised recruitment strategy template**
- **ANNEX 5 - Track record for sampling and recruiting**
- **ANNEX 6 - Communicating with vulnerable persons**
- **ANNEX 7 – Conclusions paper**

Please, notice that Annexes 4 and 5 should be filled and sent to the Project Coordinator and K-veloce I+D+I (mferrando@kveloce.com and bvallina@kveloce.com) to track and record the actions carried out by partners.

ANNEX 1 - CHECKLIST FOR IDENTIFYING STAKEHOLDERS AND POTENTIAL MULTIPLIERS

- Collective brainstorming in your organization looking for:**
 - potential stakeholders
 - associations
 - vulnerable conditions you can see on a daily basis
- Brief sociodemographic research for determining which groups could be more accessible in your community**
 - Seniors living alone
 - Migrants
 - Inmates
 - Ethnic minorities. Which one/s: _____
 - Informal caregivers
 - People receiving benefits
 - People living under the poverty threshold⁵⁹
 - Other/s: _____
- Search for Associations, NGOs, health professionals, social workers, social educators and any other group that could help you to reach these populations accessible in your own settings**
- Ask your colleagues for contacts and new ideas**
- Collect contacts from these entities and professionals compiled above (a spreadsheet would work fine)**

Entity	Name, surname	Position	Email	Telephone	Works with...	Contacted	Accepted?
<i>e.g., Association</i>					<i>Group X</i>	<i>dd/mm/yy</i>	<i>Yes/No</i>
<i>e.g., Social Work</i>					<i>Group Y</i>	<i>dd/mm/yy</i>	<i>Yes/No</i>
<i>e.g., Parish</i>					<i>Group Z</i>	<i>dd/mm/yy</i>	<i>Yes/No</i>

- Contact them and send the invitation to the workshop**
- Ask K-veloce for a contact form if you need it.**
- Considering the sample size reached, decide about the methodology: focus groups, roundtables, interviews, workshop divided into groups, etc.**

⁵⁹ Poverty Threshold in the EU-28 (by country) expressed as PPP, 2015: [http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/File:At-risk-of-poverty_threshold_\(for_a_single_person\)_currency_Purchasing_Power_Standard.png](http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/File:At-risk-of-poverty_threshold_(for_a_single_person)_currency_Purchasing_Power_Standard.png)

ANNEX 2 - TOOLS FOR WORKSHOPS – PRIORITIES AND SAMPLING

You can use this table, and adapt that if it is required, for working collaboratively in the workshop.

Please, specify in the following table which groups could be considered as a priority too (at regional-level).

Group	Characteristics	Meeting places and customs	Size	Organizations working with the group	Leaders or individuals (multipliers, seeds)	Potential exclusion criteria as regards the CDSMP

ANNEX 3 – TOOLS FOR WORKSHOPS - RECRUITMENT

You can use this table, and adapt that if it is required, for working collaboratively in the workshop.

Please, use the following table for discussing the potential strategies of identification, sampling and recruitment of vulnerable populations

Group (or individual)	Possible suitable strategy	Resources	Barriers	Case studies or Best Practices; examples

ANNEX 4 - SUMMARISED RECRUITMENT STRATEGY TEMPLATE

This document should be sent to the Project Coordinator and K-veloce to facilitate the track record of the project progress

Methodology of the National Workshop:

--

Profile and number of invited participants:

--

Conclusions

<i>Summary</i>

Inclusion criteria	Reason/s
Exclusion criteria	Reason/s

Target groups:

Target group	Multiplier group for recruiting them	Means for recruiting them	Potential collaborators	Potential sample reached	Risks	Mitigation of risks
<i>Target group 1</i>	<i>e.g., Association A, social worker C</i>	<i>e.g., direct recruitment supported by A; posters in the health centre; etc.</i>	<i>NGOs B and D Pharmacists; Parish...</i>	<i>e.g., 200 individuals/group</i>	<i>e.g., lack of sample</i>	<i>e.g., to ask for collaboration to a specific entity</i>

ANNEX 5 - TRACK RECORD FOR SAMPLING AND RECRUITING

This document should be sent to the Project Coordinator and K-veloce to facilitate the track record of the project progress

Action	Date	Place	Target group/s	Direct/Supported by a multiplier	Estimates	Impacts	Results
				<input type="checkbox"/> <i>Supported by...</i> <input type="checkbox"/> <i>Direct</i>	<i>Individuals reached</i>	<i>Individuals asking for more information</i>	<i>Individuals recruited</i>

ANNEX 6 - COMMUNICATING WITH VULNERABLE PERSONS

Design your materials (if any) **accessible and readable**

- Please, **avoid too small-sized texts** in flyers, posters, etc.
- Try to use **dark letters over light background** (and not vice versa)
- If the text is small, try to use sans-serif typographies (e.g. Arial, Helvetica, Raleway, etc.)
- Usually, we read posters, flyers and any other printable material from the upper-right corner to the lower-right corner: It would be great to keep it in mind for designing recruitment materials

Keep it **simple** and make it **easy**

- Use a simple, clear and concise language.
- For instance, a list including those chronic diseases which are more interesting for your research is more precise for all than asking for *people with chronic diseases*.
- Another example: use "high cholesterol" instead of "hypercholesterolemia", because the second one is less understandable and readable (specifically, in small flyers or questionnaires).

Do not reproduce the stigma

- For example, if you are looking for people living under the poverty threshold, do not mention that explicitly. Please, do not make reference to "low socioeconomic status" or "low socioeconomic position".

Be **careful** and **respectful** exposing your exclusion criteria:

- Making direct reference to "serious mental illness" (use "severe mental *disorders*" instead) or "addiction to drugs and alcohol" might be distressing for people with these conditions.
- Recruiters could help you to filter the specified exclusion criteria among the interested individuals.

The way we talk is important

- **Check the communication and inclusive language guidelines available in your countries** and not only from a gender-based point of view: disabilities, diseases, ethnicity, socioeconomic position and a long list of specific circumstances require **tact** for addressing and calling them. A lot of associations and foundations published guides and recommendations for this purpose⁶⁰.

In case of doubt, **ask for a double-check**

- looking for potentially stigmatising or discriminatory expressions,
- unclear messages in your materials
- or help for designing them.

⁶⁰ One example (English) about disabilities and diseases: <http://www.acedisability.org.au/information-for-providers/language-disability.php>

Co-funded by
the Health Programme
of the European Union

ANNEX 7 – CONCLUSIONS PAPER: RECRUITMENT STRATEGIES